

Funded by
the European Union

RIGOUROUS -

secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 3.2

**FIRST RESULTS OF THE MULTI-DOMAIN AUTOMATED
SECURITY ORCHESTRATION, TRUST MANAGEMENT
AND DEPLOYMENT**

Title	Deliverable D3.2 - First results of the Multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust management and deployment
Document description	This deliverable will report the first results of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment. Furthermore, this deliverable will report the scientific outcomes from the four tasks as well as the implementation aspects of the related Trust manager, AI-driven orchestrator, End-to-End multi-domain Slice Manager and the Human-Centric DevSecOps tools respectively.
Nature	Public
Task	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3. and T3.4
Status	Final
WP	WP3
Lead Partner	LNVO
Partners Involved	UWS, UMU, ORO, ITAV, ONE
Date	30/06/2024

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	LNVO	06/10/2023	Draft Table of Content
Version 02	LNVO, ALL	06 /11/2023	Consolidated and agreed Table of Contents
Version 03	ALL	20/03/2024	Initial draft inputs
Version 04	ALL, LNVO	20/04/2024	Internal Review
Version 05	ALL	05/06/2024	Final draft for project internal review
Version 06	UMU, ITAV	14/06/2024	Final review by assigned reviewers
Final Version	LNVO, UMU	28/06/2024	Final version

Disclaimer:

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2 INTRODUCTION	7
2.1. BACKGROUND	7
2.2. OBJECTIVES	7
2.3. ORGANISATION OF THE DOCUMENT	7
3 HUMAN-CENTRIC SECURITY, PRIVACY MODELING AND ONBOARDING	8
3.1. SECURITY AND PRIVACY FORMAL DATA MODELS FOR 6G NETWORKS	8
3.1.1. SYSTEM MODEL	8
3.1.2. SECURITY POLICY MODELS	9
3.1.3. COMMAND AND CONTROL POLICY	11
3.1.4. FEDERATED LEARNING	13
3.1.5. FIREWALL	14
3.2. HUMAN-CENTRIC USER-FRIENDLY TOOLS FOR DEVSECOPS AND RISK MANAGEMENT	16
3.3. ONBOARDING TOOLS	17
3.3.1 NFV SECURITY ONBOARDING SPECIFICATION	19
3.4. USER CONTROLLED VERIFIABLE SECURE DIGITAL IDENTIFICATION SERVICE	23
3.4.1. DECENTRALIZED IDENTIFIER VERIFICATION	25
3.4.2 AUTHENTICATION AND ONBOARDING USING DID IN MNO NETWORK	29
4 AI-DRIVEN CROSS-DOMAIN SECURITY AND PRIVACY ORCHESTRATION IN IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM	34
4.1. MULTI-DOMAIN AI-DRIVEN ORCHESTRATOR FOR IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM	34
4.1.1. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION	34
4.2. IOT BOOTSTRAPPING MECHANISMS	36
4.3 TRUSTED APPLICATION ONBOARDING	41
5 ZERO TRUST AND SMART SECURITY MANAGEMENT	44
5.1. TRUST EVALUATION AND TRUST ENABLER SERVICE FRAMEWORK FOR THE B5G AND 6G SYSTEM	44
5.1.1. PROTOTYPE DESIGN	44
5.1.2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS	47
6 END-TO-END MULTIDOMAIN MULTI-TENANT 6G SLICING	50

6.1. SECURITY AGENTS AND SECURITY SLICE CONTROLLERS FOR END-TO-END MULTI-DOMAIN SLICING	50
6.1.1. ORCHESTRATION OF CHANNEL-PROTECTED SECURITY SLICES	50
6.1.2. SECURITY SLICES BASED ON IPSEC FOR CHANNEL PROTECTION	51
6.1.3. SLICE MANAGER	56
6.1.4. NETWORK SELF-PROTECTION	61
7 NEXT STEPS	72
8 CONCLUSION	74
7 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	75
10 LIST OF FIGURES	79
11 LIST OF TABLES	80
12 REFERENCES	81

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the initial results of multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust management, and deployment. It reports the scientific outcomes from the following four tasks and the related implementation aspects of the Trust manager, AI-driven orchestrator, End-to-End multi-domain Slice Manager, and Human-Centric DevSecOps tools respectively. Specifically, this deliverable details the initial results from the design and prototyping of several solutions:

Task 1: Human-Centric Security, Privacy Modeling, and Onboarding:

- **Security and Privacy Formal Data Models for 6G Networks:** A comprehensive system model is developed, comprising four primary components: capacity, enablers, API, and software. Each component is elaborated to provide a detailed understanding of the system model and its functionalities. A UML diagram visually illustrates the system model and its interactions. Security policy models are defined to process Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL) policies, ensuring the security of the RIGOUROUS infrastructure. Additionally, command and control policies operate a camera using the standardized language Open Command and Control (OpenC2) for the Mobitrust use case [1]. An interoperable Federated Learning (FL) policy framework is designed to facilitate FL within the infrastructure, enabling the establishment and configuration of Security Agents. A new enabler, referencing a virtual firewall, is integrated alongside other enablers, specifically an open-source network operating system based on linux using Debian distribution VyOS [2]. A translator is developed to map policy elements to their corresponding parameters in the VyOS configuration schema, enhancing the overall security of the infrastructure.
- **Human-Centric User-Friendly Tools for DevSecOps and Risk Management:** The RIGOUROUS architecture for privacy modeling and quantification in data management involves a systematic method to quantify service privacy levels using a declarative, service-specific privacy manifest. This manifest is analyzed by a privacy quantification model employing predefined metrics and algorithms, customizable according to user preferences or regulatory standards. The architecture accommodates service updates, maintaining a privacy benchmark as the service evolves. Privacy Quantification and Management API components handle privacy risk assessment and integration into the network applications onboarding process. The approach emphasizes a human-centric perspective, empowering users to manage their privacy using the Human-Controllable Privacy UI (PUI).
- **Onboarding Tools:** The onboarding process, based on OpenSlice, includes enhancements for security, privacy, and human-centric design. The Service Composition UI (SCUI) offers end-users privacy-focused secure network applications, and the Human Controllable Privacy UI (PUI) helps developers understand service privacy scores during design. The Privacy Quantifier component computes the privacy score of entities. The Enhanced Human-Centric Virtual Network Function (VNF) Catalog Management WEB UI allows users to design Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) artifacts with privacy quantification and enhanced security controls. TM Forum (TMF) APIs and 3rd party VNF/Network Service Descriptor (NSD) Management API services provide APIs for onboarding and managing descriptors. The Intent-Based Security Management component refines security policies, while the AI-Driven Security Orchestrator translates and enforces them. The Threat Risk

Assessor (TRA) handles risk model onboarding, and the service registry enables automatic registration and discovery of services. The network applications allow dynamic mutation of network services using moving target defense (MTD) techniques to increase resilience and reduce the attack surface. The application onboarding follows a typical OpenSlice flow, onboarding NFV artifacts into the NFV-MANO and then the Service Specification into the Network Slice Orchestrator.

- **User-Controlled Verifiable Secure Digital Identification Service:** The RIGOUROUS system utilizes a Decentralized Identification and Trust Management framework with Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL) services, as described in ETSI GS PDL-012 [3] and ETSI PDL-023 [4], to enable Decentralized Identifier (DID) based authentication. This framework provides a decentralized platform for managing digital identities (allowing for globally unique identifiers), cryptographic verification data (such as DID documents and verifiable credentials), and service information. The PDL services facilitate trusted interactions between users/devices and service providers, covering aspects such as registration of DID operational participants, access control, data storage and management, decentralized identifier verification, and selective data exposure for authentication. The core PDL service functionalities form the building blocks of the decentralized identification and trust management process, enabling secure and trusted interactions in 6G systems.

Task 2: AI-Driven Cross-Domain Security and Privacy Orchestration in IoT-Edge-Cloud Continuum:

- **Security Orchestration:** The H2020 “INSPIRE-5Gplus” project features a UMU-developed security orchestrator, enhanced in the RIGOUROUS project to utilize AI for decision-making across various network layers, such as IoT, RAN, edge, core, and cloud segments, in 6G networks using FL. This AI-driven approach improves security orchestration by enabling dynamic provisioning, deployment, and reconfiguration of virtual network security functions during operation. Despite challenges in policy definition, security enforcement, and interoperability, the flexibility of orchestration is expected to enhance protection, detection, and remediation strategies. A policy-based approach standardizes security management in complex 5G infrastructures by defining security requirements clearly and enhancing system consistency. The workflow for End-to-End (E2E) orchestration involves receiving high-level security policies, performing conflict detection, identifying required capabilities across domains, retrieving endpoint information, requesting common parameters, refining policies, creating an enforcement plan, and enforcing policies according to priority and dependencies. This comprehensive process ensures effective orchestration and enforcement of security policies across different network segments.
- **IoT Bootstrapping Mechanisms:** The IoT device bootstrapping specification outlines how IoT devices connect to a network for authentication and secure connection setup, as well as how they obtain long-term credentials securely. Initially, IoT devices connect to an onboarding network using default credentials. They then retrieve long-term credentials, known as Attribute-Based Credentials (ABC) Verifiable Credentials, from a provisioning server. These ABC credentials act as the digital identity of the IoT device, allowing it to authenticate itself in untrusted sub-networks, access network applications, use 6G

services, and even authenticate and connect directly with other devices in a device-to-device (D2D) interaction, as long as both devices trust the credential issuer.

- **Trusted Application Onboarding:** Applications disclose how they handle data, especially private data, allowing for creating different versions of the same application with varying privacy features or different applications providing the same function with different privacy characteristics. Applications offering more privacy might integrate additional services or enhancements. In the described process, a user device (UE) receives a fingerprint of the genuine application developer certificates for a specific application, identified by its application ID. A credential previously issued by the NANCY (An Artificial Intelligent Aided Unified Network for Secure Beyond 5G Long Term Evolution) Identity (ID) Issuer includes an attribute listing the applications the network wants to manage with specific rules, protected by the Issuer's public key for security. Another attribute in the credential contains the address of the Certified Application Server (CAS). The CAS compiles a list of application IDs and certificate fingerprints, encrypts this list with the UE's public key, and sends it to the UE.

Task 3: Zero Trust and Smart Security Management:

- **Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service Framework (TESF) for the Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G Systems:** A standalone system is developed to perform security/trust evaluations and assign trust scores based on security evaluation results (related to deviations from expected/specified standard behaviors e.g., behavior violations over communication interfaces and statistics from various entities such as end-user devices (UEs), RAN, Core NFs (using Service Based Interfaces (SBI)) and application functions (AFs). These trust scores help network and management entities make timely decisions during network operations and orchestration to mitigate network risks and threats. The process involves three main steps: data collection, abnormal behavior event i.e., violation translation, and trust score assignment by the TESF. The TESF can also trigger an AI-driven decision engine to respond to significant trust-based violations. This section details the TESF system design, the technologies and procedures used, the types of attacks considered, and initial unit test results of the standalone TESF.

Task 4: End-to-End Multidomain Multi-Tenant 6G Slicing:

- To secure network slices across different domains, security agents and slice controllers are essential. Security agents monitor and manage network elements, collect data from devices for security decisions, and enforce security measures from the orchestrator. Security slice controllers create and implement channel protection policies for network slices as directed by the security orchestrator.

Within each section, based on the development stage of each of the WP3 assets, an initial implementation and preliminary result is presented. Furthermore, the current achievements and the future direction of this line of research is mapped for further advancement of this work package.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1. Background

Deliverable D3.2 presents the initial findings and outcomes of the RIGUROUS project, which aims to create a secure and trustworthy 6G ecosystem. The document focuses on the first results of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust management, and deployment. It covers the design and prototyping of various key solutions specific to the WP3 tasks, such as:

- Human-Centric security, privacy modeling, and onboarding
- AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum
- Zero trust and Smart security management
- End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing.

The report elaborates on the scientific outcomes of the four tasks and provides detailed insights into the implementation aspects of the Trust manager, AI-driven orchestrator, End-to-End multi-domain Slice Manager, and Human-Centric DevSecOps tools. The document also outlines the project's future steps and conclusions.

2.2. Objectives

The objectives of this deliverable are in line with the objectives of WP3 and the overall project objectives, especially Objective 1 Holistic Smart Service framework for securing the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum lifecycle management, Objective 2 Human-Centric DevSecOps, and Objective 3 Model-based and AI-driven Automated Security Orchestration, Trust Management, and deployment. In particular, this deliverable aims to achieve the following:

- In relation to Objective 1, based on D2.1, 'System Requirements Analysis Report', this deliverable further develops the functional architecture of the framework by specifying the architecture of multi-domain orchestration.
- In relation to Objective 2, this deliverable describes the design and prototyping of the human-centric security and privacy modeling and onboarding.
- In relation to Objective 3, this deliverable describes the design and prototyping of the AI-driven orchestration, zero-trust security management, and end-to-end multi-domain network slicing.

2.3. Organisation of the document

The rest of the document is structured as follows. Clause 3 presents the human-centric security, privacy modeling and onboarding aspects along with detailed information on system model; tools for DevSecOps, risk management, onboarding; and enablers for secure digital identification service. Clause 4 details the AI driven cross-domain security and privacy orchestration aspect for IoT-edge-cloud continuum and Clause 5 elaborates the Zero trust and smart security management. Further, Clause 6 describes the End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing aspects. Finally, Clause 7 provides an overview of next steps in the view of the RIGUROUS future work and Clause 8 concludes the deliverable.

3 HUMAN-CENTRIC SECURITY, PRIVACY MODELING AND ONBOARDING

3.1. Security and Privacy formal data models for 6G networks

3.1.1. System model

We use the system model to declare the structure of the components inside the orchestrator. These are declared inside a file named *initial-data.yaml*, here there are four principal components that includes capability, enablers, API and software. Examples of these components are shown below in Figure 1-4.

The first component is capability. This component defines the name of the specific function or action that is available within the policies. Capabilities are essentially the predefined operations that a system or device can perform.

```
- model: software.capability
  pk: 23
  fields:
    name: fl_agent
    creation_date: "DATETIME"
    last_update: "DATETIME"
```

Figure 1. System Capabilities.

The second component is the enabler, this component declares the principal available enablers that we can use, deploy, and configure through the policies.

```
- model: software.enabler
  pk: 30
  fields:
    name: agent
    capabilities: [23]
    domains: []
    creation_date: "DATETIME"
    last_update: "DATETIME"
```

Figure 2. System Enablers.

Finally, we specify the software and API dependencies necessary for the system to function correctly. Additionally, we outline the endpoint URL and the protocol (such as HTTP, HTTPS, or WebSocket) for the connection configuration, providing clear instructions on how to connect and interact with the API. This comprehensive specification ensures that all components can communicate seamlessly, and the system operates as intended.

devices. Our plan is to extend this behavior to also be able to secure traffic in multi-domain software defined networks (SDN) environments. Other security policy models include filtering and firewall features, that also provide security measures to prevent and react to network attacks.

Figure 5 shows the definition of security policy models in the system model schema. We can see that the policy has a parameter named "spd", of type "SPD", that is defined in Figure 6. We can see then that the SPD definition contains a pair of parameters for IP addresses ("localAddress" and "remoteAddress"), the IPsec protection mode (transport or tunnel), and the SAD (Security Association Database), defined in Figure 7. There, we can see that the SAD is composed of the parameters needed for packet security: "encryptionAlgorithm" and "integrityAlgorithm" contain algorithms for encryption and integrity, "encryptionKey" and "integrityKey" contain the shared secret used to secure the messages (there are two instances of each one, as in bidirectional communication two pairs of different shared secrets are used to create SAs (Security Associations=: one for incoming traffic, and another for outgoing traffic), "enclv" contains an initialization vector, a random string that some algorithms need to add more randomness to the encryption process, and lastly two sets of parameters, one starting with the prefix "soft" ("softByte", "softPackets", "softAdded" and "softUsed"), and another starting with "hard" ("hardByte", "hardPackets", "hardAdded" and "hardUsed"). Both sets represent the lifetime for the IPsec SAs, but each one has a different meaning. The "soft" lifetimes indicate when the SA needs to be renewed (in a process named rekey), but it is still valid until the "hard" lifetime is reached. After the "hard" lifetime moment, the SA is removed from the device, so it should have been renewed before to avoid traffic loss between the devices.

```
<complexType name="SecurityConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ParametersSecurityConfigurationCondition" />
  </complexContent>
</complexType>

<complexType name="ParametersSecurityConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="spd"
          type="ITResource:SPD"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 5 Security Policy models definition in System Model schema.

```
<complexType name="SPD">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="localAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="remoteAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="1" name="modeType" type="ITResource:SecureModeType"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="sad" type="ITResource:SAD"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 6. SPD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema.

```
<complexType name="SAD">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encryptionAlgorithm" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="2" minOccurs="0" name="encryptionKey" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encIv" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="integrityAlgorithm" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="2" minOccurs="0" name="intKey" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softByte" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softPackets" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softAdded" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="softUsed" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardByte" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardPackets" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardAdded" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="hardUsed" type="string"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 7. SAD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema.

3.1.3. Command and control policy

To operate the camera, we are using OASIS OpenC2. OpenC2 is a standardized language used for command and control of cyber defense technologies. It facilitates the coordination and automation of defense actions across different systems. In the context of managing a camera, OpenC2 commands could be used to direct the camera's operations, such as turning it on or off, changing its settings, or capturing images, all through a common, machine-readable format that ensures interoperability between different security devices and platforms.

Figure 8 shows the most important part of the schema declaration for creating command and control policies, in this case to control a camera.

```
<complexType name="CommandControlRuleAction">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationAction">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="commandControlActionType" type="ITResource:CommandControlActionType"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="ruleParameters" type="ITResource:CommandControlConfigurationCondition"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 8. CommandControlRuleAction definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.

As we can see in Figure 9, as for the type of command and control we only declare CAMERA, this can be extended for future contributions.

```
<simpleType name="CommandControlActionType">
  <restriction base="string">
    <enumeration value="CAMERA"/>
  </restriction>
</simpleType>
```

Figure 9. CommandControlActionType definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.

Based on this, the main elements of camera operation using OpenC2 are shown in Figure 10. These elements are request, response, action, device_id, driver_device_id and command_id. The request and response elements provide a way to determine if the OpenC2 message corresponds with a request from the Security Orchestrator to the camera, or a response from the camera to the Security Orchestrator. The action element contains the action to enforce in the camera (which for the Mobitrust use case, the available values are "stoprecording" and "stopstreaming", to stop the camera recording or streaming, respectively). Lastly, the device_id and driver_device_id identify the target camera and the driver it's running.

```
<complexType name="CameraRuleParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="request" type="boolean"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="response" type="boolean"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="action" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="macAddress" type="string"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="command_id" type="string"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 10. CameraRuleParameters definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.

3.1.4. Federated Learning

To establish and configure the requisite elements for FL within the infrastructure as Security Agents, an interoperable and inventive FL policy framework was devised, encapsulating all critical details. The FL configuration policy, in conjunction with the plugin and driver implemented in the orchestrator, detailed in D3.1 allows the deployment of both FL agents and FL aggregators dynamically and on-demand (based on the needs), so a new detection model, updated with the current status of the network, can be trained by means of FL to replace the existing model in the detection engine, without having to stop the detection process for this purpose.

The federated learning policy templates are intended to represent the configuration needed in a federated learning system. Some of these parameters are defined in Figure 11.

```
<complexType name="FilterFLConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="instanceThreshold" type="integer" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="aggregatorParameters" type="ITResource:AggregatorParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="localConnectionParameters" type="ITResource:LocalConnectionParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="integrationFabricParameters" type="ITResource:IntegrationFabricParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="learningModelInfo" type="ITResource:LearningModelInfo" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="learningParameters" type="ITResource:LearningParameters" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="obfuscationInfo" type="ITResource:ObfuscationInfo" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 11. FilterFLConfigurationCondition definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.

Some of the most important data types are shown in Figure 12, containing some of the most significant parameters.

```
<complexType name="AggregatorParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="URL" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="rounds" type="integer" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="fusionAlgorithm" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="apiPort" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="minClients" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 12. AggregatorParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.

In Figure 13 we can see the learning parameters that can be introduced in federated learning policies.

```
<complexType name="LearningParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="testSize" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="localEpochs" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="batchSize" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="stepsPerEpoch" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 13. LearningParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.

3.1.5. Firewall

With the aim to provide security to the RIGUROUS infrastructure, a new enabler is developed, which makes reference to a virtual firewall and is integrated like all other enablers. We have chosen VyOS as our open-source firewall solution [2]. VyOS is based on Debian and offers great flexibility. One of its key strengths is its ability to be deployed rapidly using Docker and Kubernetes, enabling dynamic deployment when needed.

First of all, we generate a policy to configure the firewall to drop messages from a specific IP address. Following the setup of the post request, we proceed to develop a translator capable of parsing the input policy received from our orchestrator and converting it into an output in JSON format containing the main configuration parameters required by VyOS. This translator acts as a crucial intermediary component in our deployment pipeline, as it enables seamless communication between the input policy format, which may vary depending on our internal conventions or the requirements of other systems, and the specific configuration format expected by VyOS.

By implementing this translator, we ensure that the input policy is accurately interpreted and translated into a format that VyOS can readily understand and apply. This includes mapping policy elements such as firewall rules, network settings, and security configurations to their corresponding parameters in the VyOS configuration schema. Additionally, the translator may perform validation and normalization tasks to ensure that the generated configuration adheres to VyOS's syntax and constraints, thereby minimizing the risk of configuration errors or inconsistencies.

Once the translation process is complete, the output JSON containing the configured parameters is ready to be included in the post request payload sent to VyOS via curl. This seamless integration of translation and deployment processes enables efficient and reliable configuration management, facilitating the automation of network provisioning and ensuring consistency across our infrastructure.

The main parameters that we need to configure the firewall are as follows, destinationAddress, action, sourceAddress and name, as depicted in Figure 17.

```
<complexType name="RuleParameters">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="destinationAddress" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="action" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="sourceAddress" type="string" />
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="name" type="string" />
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 17. RuleParameters definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema.

3.2. Human-centric user-friendly tools for DevSecOps and risk management

We aim to formalize privacy modeling within data management through a systematic method, quantifying service privacy levels using a declarative, and service-specific privacy manifest.

The privacy manifest, a statement outlining privacy service definitions, undergoes analysis by a privacy quantification model that employs predefined metrics and algorithms to assess the service's privacy level. This quantification can be customized according to user preferences or regulatory standards, and it is crucial for distinguishing between similar services or enabling benchmarking. The quantification result is an analysis executed over the application and/or its description and provides a privacy related score. Depending on the application, and the developer's approach, we consider two sources for this score: developer provided information, and automatically assessed information. The first method results from the developer specifically stating the data processing characteristics of the application, including which data is processed, which data is stored and how, and which data is communicated with specific external endpoints. These endpoints relate to external services on a Service Cloud. The second approach relies on tools that estimate how data is processed/stored and which is the connectivity graph with external endpoints. As stated, both methods result in a quantification and composite score.

Additionally, our proposed architecture accommodates service updates. It establishes a control version to maintain a privacy benchmark as the service evolves. The privacy quantification component is utilized to re-evaluate the privacy level of the updated service, thereby updating the final metric.

This approach establishes a continuous cycle of privacy testing and monitoring (DevPrivOps). Privacy quantification and re-quantification ensure ongoing assessment and refinement of the service's privacy practices. This iterative approach promotes continual enhancement of privacy practices, aligning the service with evolving privacy standards and best practices.

Considering the previously described architecture of RIGOUROUS, we intend to create two components named Privacy Quantification and Management API. These external services will be responsible for privacy risk assessment and its integration into the network applications onboarding process.

For privacy quantification, we will consider a set of indicators based on metrics applied to Software Quality Assurance (SQA) and applicable legislation considering data in transit across multiple jurisdictions.

Through the Management API, we also plan to utilize the output of the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA), an internal component of RIGOUROUS, to quantify or re-quantify the privacy level offered by network services.

The manifest file should encompass all aspects of the network service. The privacy quantification component will use this file to compare the expected privacy requirements (based on the indicators) for a specific service with the content in the file. After quantification, we also intend to use the content of the privacy manifest file for slicing selection during the onboarding process.

The deployment and testing phases of network application onboarding will also benefit from privacy quantification. The privacy quantification component will analyze and test new software versions (control version).

By emphasizing the proposition of a human-centric approach, we aim to empower users with the capability to manage their privacy using the Human-Controllable Privacy UI (PUI). Users should have the ability to assess the privacy levels provided by the network service, make informed decisions regarding its usage, and, when necessary, receive suggestions for more appropriate alternatives.

3.3. Onboarding tools

OpenSlice is an open-source operations support system (OSS) which helps deliver Network Slices as a Service (NSaaS) and was recently endorsed by ETSI into a standard development group. It allows service developers to onboard their network applications to a target network functions virtualization orchestrator (NFVO), using standardized Open APIs for that purpose.

OpenSlice ships with a service catalog, whereby the vertical end-users can browse available network applications, similar to an online marketplace, and place orders for the desired application. After the order is placed and, subsequently accepted, the necessary network services (and composing virtual network functions (VNFs)) are instantiated. These operations make use of TeleManagement Forum (TMF)'s well-known APIs, such as Service Specification, Service Order and Service Inventory.

Another key feature of OpenSlice is the onboarding, through one of the portals, of the required VNF and network service (NS) descriptors to the management and orchestration (MANO) provider; To achieve this, OpenSlice utilizes the ETSI NFV-SOL 005 interface.

As such, OpenSlice is the perfect starting point to augment the onboarding of the network applications, with privacy and security concerns.

Figure 18. The onboarding diagram.

The onboarding diagram (present in Figure 18) is first introduced in deliverable D3.1, ‘Design plan of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management and deployment’ and shares a number of components present in OpenSlice, including some that are to be enhanced with regards to the security and privacy considerations, all while privileging the human-centric factor.

- The Service Composition UI (SCUI) is an extension to the services portal of OpenSlice. The goal is to offer the end-users privacy-focused secure network applications. For that, the service specifications must be extended with new attributes pertaining to these characteristics. Additionally, the development of these services must be user-friendly and the developers should have tools that assist them in the design of network services with a high privacy score - this is achieved through the Human Controllable Privacy UI (PUI).
- The PUI makes the privacy quantification of the network applications accessible to developers in the form of a numerical scale. This quantification is done in real-time, helping the network developers to understand the privacy score of the services in every step of the design process.
- The Privacy Quantifier component was briefly discussed in deliverable D3.1 and is responsible for the computation of the privacy score associated with an entity, which is then consumed by the PUI. This calculation includes not only the descriptions of the network services and NFV artifacts, but also user inputs and other metadata.

- The Enhanced Human Centric VNF Catalog Management WEB UI is based on OpenSlice's NFV portal, which lets users onboard the VNF descriptors (VNFDs) or the NS descriptors (NSDs) to the facility's NFVO/MANO. The "Enhanced Human Centric" portion of the name involves allowing the design of the NFV artifacts in a human-centric manner and with the presence of the privacy quantification, provided by the PUI component. Moreover, the VNF descriptors (VNFDs) and NSDs are to be endowed with the enhanced security and privacy controls.
- The TMF APIs service is a component offered by OpenSlice which provides TMF interfaces for describing and interacting with services, most notably TMF Service Catalog, TMF Service Ordering and TMF Service Inventory. The first provides mechanisms to query and manage the Service Specification Catalog, while the last two offer methods for ordering a service from the catalog and getting information about running network services, respectively.
- The 3rd party VNF/NSD Management API service is a OpenSlice functional block which offers APIs for onboarding the descriptors to the target MANO and their management thereafter.
- The Application Onboarding UI (AOUI) was explained in chapter 3 of deliverable D3.1. In short, it is tasked with configuring the Policy Control Function (PCF) of the network core.
- The Intent Based Security Management component permits the definition and automatic refinement of the security service level agreements (SSLAs) and security policies (SPs), deploying and enforcing them, dynamically. It is responsible for the refinement of the high-level technology-agnostic policy models defined using HSPL-OP into medium-level configurations, detecting any possible conflicts that may arise. These medium-level policies are then passed to the AI Driven Security Orchestrator for translation.
- The AI Driven Security Orchestrator (SO) takes the medium-level policies represented in MSPL-OP, translates them to the low-level technology-specific configurations and enforces them in the local domain. Furthermore, it interacts with the MANO for the deployment of the configurations and does the Security Onboarding, which is explained later in this section.
- The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) component is responsible for the Risk Model Onboarding, which is also discussed below.
- Finally, the Service registry allows for automatic registration and discovery of the services.

Additionally, the network applications should allow for dynamic mutation of the network services, by employing moving target defense (MTD) techniques, including changing the port numbers used by services, switching the ciphers used to encrypt data or switching between different underlying technologies. This functionality intends to increase the resilience of the network by, simultaneously, increasing its availability and reducing the attack surface.

3.3.1 NFV Security Onboarding Specification

The application onboarding follows a typical OpenSlice flow, as shown in Figure 19. First, the NFV artifacts are onboarded into the NFV-MANO. Then, the Service Specification is onboarded into the Network Slice Orchestrator, referencing the previously onboarded NFV artifacts that may be required.

The Security Onboarding can be done via the Intent-based Security Formal Modeling (SMUI) or via the Security Orchestrator (SO). Both flows are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21 respectively.

Figure 19. Application onboarding follows a typical OpenSlice flow.

Figure 20. Security Onboarding via Intent-based Security Formal Modeling.

Figure 21. Security Onboarding via Security Orchestrator.

The Risk Model is onboarded via the Risk Management UI (RiMUI) into the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA), as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Risk Model onboarding via the Risk Management UI.

Similarly, the Response Playbooks are onboarded via the Response-Mitigation Policies (ReMUI) into the Response-Mitigation (RM), as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Response Playbooks onboarding via the Response-Mitigation Policies into the Response-Mitigation.

Service Composition is possible via the SCUI that will onboard the Service Composition Description into the Dynamic Service Composer (DSC), as shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Service Composition via the SCUI into the Dynamic Service Composer.

Synchronization and consistency across the different orchestrators can be achieved via additional payload in the service definition and pre-flight checks. Performing such check would impose dependencies on the onboarding sequence, as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Dependencies on the onboarding sequence.

3.4. User controlled verifiable secure digital identification service

A Decentralized Identification and Trust management framework with PDL services described in the PDL reference architecture ETSI GS PDL-012 [2] and ETSI PDL-023 [3] can be used by the RIGOROUS system to enable the DID based authentication (i.e., usage of DID management services and specifically the DID verifications operations based on PDL services for authentication as shown in Figure 26 for the 6G systems. The Decentralized Identification and Trust management framework provided PDL services can be consumed by the onboarding network (Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN)/Non-Public Networks (NPN) in telecom scenario) for the UE onboarding and subsequent authentication for the services. A DID described in this section can be referred as decentralized identity/digital identity/self-sovereign identity.

The present document uses a functional block architecture to define various PDL services required to enable a decentralized identification and trust management framework. A decentralized platform has the capability to facilitate a globally unique digital identifier (i.e., DID with no possibility of duplication) related data management and control of associated cryptographic verification data, service information, etc. as needed for decentralized identification and authentication of a DID holder (i.e., user/device) to setup trusted interactions between the DID holder and a service provider for any related digital service provisions. The procedural aspects of PDL based decentralized identification and trust management ranges from different participants registration along with access control over the decentralized identification system, related data storage and management operations (e.g., throughout the data lifecycle), the decentralized identifier verification, and selective data exposure to service provider(s) for end-user/device authentication respectively.

Figure 26. Decentralized Identification and Trust management framework (DTMF).

The core PDL service functionalities (i.e., capabilities, behavior, and relationships) forms the building block of decentralized identification and trust management process which includes the following as shown in Figure 26 and it is described in detail below:

- **Ledger Role-based registration management service:** The ledger role-based registration management service (L-RMS) considers the following different roles for the participants who are the integral users of the decentralized identification and trust management framework. It provides registration service (along with authorization for fine grained access control) specific to the corresponding roles of the participants and their allowed operations in the PDL platform. The role-based registration management service offers registration and de-registration (e.g., revocation of registration) related services for different participants:
 - Identity Holder (i.e., a DID Holder);
 - Identity Controller (i.e., a DID Controller);
 - VC Issuer; and
 - DID Verifier.
- **DID Operational participants Registry service:** The DID Operational participants registry service (DPRS) records and keeps track of the registered and de-registered participants from the PDL platform based Decentralized Identification and Trust management framework (DTMF) by considering the instructions from the L-RMS.
- **DID Resolver service:** The DID Resolver service (DRS) stores the DIDs in a DID registry, keeps track of the DID(s) and its associated DID document location information (e.g., address) to enable DID document fetching and verification by the authorized services and entities (i.e., DID Verifiers e.g., service providers).
- **DID Document Registry service:** The DID Document Registry service (DDRS) allows to store and manage the DID documents associated to the DID to facilitate DID verification. Whereas each DID Document can contain at least three things: proof purposes, service specific information for which the DID document can be used, verification methods, and service endpoints. Proof purposes are combined with verification methods to provide mechanisms for proving things.

For example, a DID Document can specify that a particular verification method, such as a cryptographic public key or pseudonymous biometric protocol, can be used to verify a proof that was created for the purpose of authentication.

Service endpoints enable trusted interactions with the DID holder as well as authorized verifier. The DID Document Registry service offers Create (i.e., to store), Update, Revoke DID documents (i.e., deletion) related service operations.

- **VC Data Registry service:** The VC Data Registry service (VDRS) allows to store and manage the verifiable credentials (VCs) associated to the DID to facilitate VC based DID verification and validation related to a service request. The VC Data Registry service offers Create, Update, and Revoke VCs related service operations.

- **DID Verification management service:** The DID verification management service (DVMS) can be a composite service (ETSI GS PDL 012) that uses DID resolver service, DID document registry service, DID operation(al) participant registry service and VC Data Registry service to fetch necessary data related to verification of DID (i.e., authentication of the subject identified by the DID), and performs exposure of selective data to the verifier to enable authentication of the subject and authorization verification of subject to respective service(s).

3.4.1. Decentralized Identifier Verification

3.4.1.1. Introduction

This clause describes how the PDL platform based DTMF described in clause 3.4 is used to perform two main aspects such as:

- i) DID based DID holder authentication; and
- ii) authorization.

Decentralized Identifier verification service is a composite service [as in ETSI PDL-012] which consumes various services offered by DTMF such as DID resolver service, DID document registry service, DID operation(al) participant registry service and VC Data Registry service to fetch DID associated data (such as DID, DID documents and VCs) to enable DID verification by the authorized verifiers (e.g., a service provider). DID Verification process allows DTMF to expose the DID documents and selective data (i.e., based on the associated VCs) to the appropriate verifier for:

- i) authentication of the subject identified by the DID; and
- ii) authorization check specific to the subject to provide the allowed service(s).

The detailed DID verification process is described further in clause 3.4.1.2.

3.4.1.2. DID verification process

The DID verification process is handled using DID verification management service, DID resolver service, DID Operational participants Registry service, DID Document Registry service and VC Data Registry service using the steps shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27. DID verification for DID holder authentication and authorization.

Precondition 1: The DID holder/controller already creates, stores, and manages the DID and DID documents over the DTMF based on ETSI PDL-023 [3]; and the DID holder being the UE, request access to the Operator’s network to consume operator’s service or a 3rd party service (for which the operator network and 3rd party service provider has service level agreement (SLA) to offer the 3rd party’s service over the operator’s network). The UE sent request (e.g., registration request or onboarding request) contains the DID managed over the DTMF. The DID can take the format as NAI (e.g., can contain the information as defined by the W3C consortium for DID). The DID holder and the DID Verifier are registered to the DTMF based on PDL-023 to perform various PDL services as required.

1. The DID holder sends to the DID Verifier a service request (or any access request) with DID for a service provision. Based on the type of DTMF implementation, a DID verification management service and DID resolver service can be co-located or standalone.

The service request message that is being sent between the DID holder (i.e., end-device client/application) and the DID verifier (application server/service provider) can be over the Non-Access Stratum (NAS) interface as per TS 23.502 [5]. The AMF in the 3GPP network, based on DID sends an authentication request to the responsible application

function/service handling the decentralized authentication service. Steps 1 and 14 happen in 3GPP network and it may be external to the PDL framework. An application function/server in the 3GPP network can take the role of DID verifier (e.g., an authenticator).

2. The DID verifier determines to use the DID Verification Service offered by the DTMF based on the DID (e.g., using realm or information in the DID).
 - a. The DID verifier sends to the DID verification service a DID verification request message with the DID verifier's source ID, DID, target DID service type (i.e., the type of service for which the DID is being associated to the DID holder and being verified by the DID verifier).
3. If no secure connection exists between the DID Verifier and the DID verification service, both can perform mutual authentication (using Security Platform Services in ETSI GS PDL 012 [2]) and set up a secure connection.
4. The DID Verification service sends to the DID Verifier an Authorization data request message with source identity.
5. The DID Verifier responds to the DID Verification service, it sends an Authorization data response message which includes its Registration ID and its corresponding authorization information (received during role-based registration described in PDL-023 [3] clause 5.2.2.1).
6. The DID Verification service sends to the DID Operation(al) participants Registry service, an Authorization verification request message, which includes the registration ID (of the DID verifier), authorization information (i.e., an authorization code or token as received), access role "set as DID verifier", and for verifiers additionally the service type information (received in step 2).
7. The DID Operation(al) participant registry service verifies the authorization information and access role related to the Registration ID (e.g., by querying the respective ledger for related transaction records or by checking an offline/local storage) to check if the access role, authorization information and registration ID matches the records related to the registered participant. For the DID verifiers, additionally the target DID service type information is also checked to see if it is allowed based on the records.
8. If the verification of the registration ID, access role, target DID service type, and authorization information are successful, then the Registry service sends to the DID Verification Service, an authorization verification response message with the registration ID (of the Verifier) and result as "successful".

If the verification of the registration ID, access role, target DID service type, and authorization information do not match with the records, then the Registry service sends to the DID Verification Service, an authorization verification response message, with the registration ID, and result as "failure". Further directly step 13 is performed related to the failure case.

9. The DID Verification services invoke the DID resolver service (i.e., co-located with the DID verification service) and fetch the DID related DID Document Registry address. The DID verification service sends to the DID Document Registry service, a DID verification data request, which includes a DID.
10. a - b:

- a. The DID Document registry service checks if the DID document is available (e.g., in a ledger/chain) for the DID. Further if the DID document is available, the DID document service based on local configuration also finds the VC registry service address and sends to the VC registry service, a VC request message, with the DID.
 - b. The VC Registry service fetches the VCs associated to the DID (e.g., from the respective chain/ledger) and sends to the DID document registry service, a VC response message with the DID and the associated VC(s).
11. The DID Document Registry service fetches the DID document(s) related to the DID and generates the VC metadata from the VCs to enable the DID Verifier to authenticate and authorize the DID as required for the service provision.
 12. The DID Document Registry service then sends to the DID Verification service, a DID verification data response, with DID, DID documents, and the VC metadata (based on the VCs i.e., claims asserted related to the DID holder specific to the service).
 13. The DID Verification service sends to the DID Verifier, a DID Verification response message, which includes result (with successful indication), DID document, and VC metadata (related to VCs).

For the failure case operations, the DID Verification service sends to the DID verifier, a DID verification response message with result set as "failure indication", and cause information (i.e., such as violation code/authorization failure/authentication failure respectively).

14. The DID Verifier can use the DID documents to verify (i.e., to integrity check and authenticate) the DID, and authenticate the DID holder (e.g., related subject). Further the DID verifier can also use the metadata (derived from the VCs) associated to the DID subject to verify the authorization provided for the DID subject, specific to the requested service provision. If the verification of the DID, authentication of the DID subject and the VCs metadata meets the service requirement criteria then the DID verifier sends to the end-device (i.e., DID holder), a Service response message, which can include a successful result. Following which the DID holder will be provided with the requested service. A key associated from the DID document can also be used to set up an initial secure communication between the DID holder and the DID Verifier.

The metadata based on the VCs can enable to authenticate the subject based on the service specific criteria which are asserted by the claims of the VCs linked to the documents such as passport, driving license, any government issued ID card, college/degree certificate, etc. For example, the VCs may assert claims to prove the service requirements e.g. a service requirement may be the DID holder should be of age above 15 to consume a service (or) the DID holder should belong to a location to consume a service, the DID holder should belong to a country or university or company to consume a service (or) the DID holder should hold a valid driving license to consume a service, etc.

For the failure case operation, the DID Verifier can consider as authentication failed and deny the service request by sending to the end-device (i.e., DID holder), a Service response message with the result as failure and the cause information via the 3GPP network.

3.4.2 Authentication and onboarding using DID in MNO network

Figure 28. DID/SSI based Subscription Onboarding for Network Access during Registration Procedure.

The message flow shown in above Figure 28 can be adopted to a scenario where the PLMN/NPN network operator performs DID user identity authentication via ID/Trust service provider Infrastructure/Decentralized ID Framework (or a PDL framework) to trigger onboarding and provisioning of Mobile Network Operator (MNO)'s PLMN/NPN/3rd party service provider's subscription to the UE. The message flow is described below.

1. The UE (can be any mobile user equipment or IoT device) sends the registration request message to the AMF (over a NAS message) which contains an onboarding indication and a DID with Timestamp (TS) and related digital signature (DS) of DID and Timestamp. So, the UE sends DID + Timestamp + Signature.
The TS is added in addition to the DID by the UE while sending in the registration request. The timestamp is used by the UE to prevent any attacker from reusing the cached DID for replay attack.

A digital signature for the DID along with the timestamp is created by the UE to integrity protect the DID along with the proof of possession of the private key by the credential owner (i.e., a UE/User).

A DID can be integrity protected in any of the two options, i.e., case 1 is by mean of digital signature and case 2 is by means of generating a message authentication code tag as described below. Method of digital signature can be similar to the process mentioned in case 1.

The DID, Timestamp and Digital signature (of DID and Time stamp) (DID_TS with DS) is sent in the registration request to the network by the UE.

- Case 1: Digital Signature can be used for DID integrity protection
The digital signature of the DID is generated by the UE and is used to prove the proof of possession of private key used to protect the DID. The scheme output will contain the digital signature of the DID.
 - Preconditions for Digital Signature Creation - UE and the Service Provider (MNO/Trust Service Provider (TSP)/Identification service Provider (IDP)) has any Certificates (example X.509, Verifiable Certificate etc.,) to support PKI. During online sign up with a Service Provider, UEs are provided certificates with a signed public key for the network in which they are allowed to connect. The TSP would likewise be provided with certificates of eligible UEs.
 - Each Service Provider has a public and private key pair (sp_PUB_Key, sp_PRI_Key).
 - UEs have a corresponding public and private key pair (UE_PUB_Key, UE_PRI_Key).
 - Each Service Provider shares its public key (sp_PUB_Key) with a certificate with all UEs.
 - UEs share their public keys (UE_PUB_Key) with a certificate with the Service Provider.
 - (Optionally) - If there is a different network operator who need to provide access to Service provider's subscribers then Network Operator can be provisioned with the same sp_PRI_Key.
 - Create a message digest by applying a hashing algorithm to the DID.
 - Encrypt the digest with the core network UE_PRI_Key which becomes the signature.
 - The signature is appended to the Actual Message.

 - Case 2: Alternatively, shared secret key can be used to generate the MAC tag of the DID. The scheme output will contain the MAC tag of the DID.
If a DID is used as Digital ID, then the DID Information can include any DID syntax-based information from W3C Working Draft of DIDs. Example: Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) scheme identifier (did), Identifier for the DID method, DID method-specific identifier.
2. The AMF sends the authentication request message (i.e., Nausf_UEAuth_Request) to the AUSF with the Onboarding indication, receiving DID_TS with DS.

3. The AUSF on receiving an onboarding indication with DID_TS with DS sends an authentication data request message (i.e., Nudm_UEAuth_Request) to the UDM with the received Onboarding indication and DID_TS with DS.
4. Based on the DID type, the UDM can determine to invoke verification of DID through the ID Service/Trust service provider who manages/controls the DID and related DID documents (verifiable user/device credentials).
5. Based on the ID Service/Trust service provider information present in the DID, the UDM selects the ID/Trust service provider and sends a subscriber ID verification request message with the received DID along with a Key request indication to the ID/Trust service provider. The message may contain additional information request indication about the subscriber/user, e.g., name, address, day of birth, bank account, etc. in order to generate a full subscription profile. The ID/Trust service provider can together form a Digital Identity Service platform.
6. The ID/Trust service provider on receiving a DID_TS with DS verifies the DID based on a universal resolver or local database information which stores the association of the DID and the address of the DID documents storage in a Blockchain/PDL. The ID/Trust service provider verifies the validity, scope of DID usage (scope refers to the usage information related to the DID which clarifies the purpose for which the DID can be used by the user/network) and authenticity of the DID by fetching the DID information and user documents (verifiable credentials). If any NF (here the UDM, or it can also be a subscription provisioning server/onboarding server) from service provider/MNO domain requests any subscriber related information, then the ID/Trust service provider generates a Minimum data set with all required subscription information about the subscriber/user (a minimum data set for example can contain subscriber name, location, DID validity, service payment info, service activation status etc.,).
In addition, if the service provider also requests a security key to protect the subscription onboarding, then ID Service/Trust service provider derives the Onboarding Root key ($K_{\text{ONB_Root}}$) based on the security credentials available (example: a public / private key pair and a shared secret key) in the UE.
Onboarding Key ($K_{\text{ONB_Root}}$) = KDF (Shared Secret Key, MNO/Service provider ID)

Method of Digital Signature Verification: If the digital signature is applied for a DID_TS, then at the service provider side, the service provider should use the corresponding UE_PUB_Key to verify the signature of DID_TS. If the signature is successfully verified, Service provider can accept the messages; otherwise, the messages are discarded, and the verification result will be set to failure in step 7.
7. The ID/Trust service provider sends to UDM (or an NF in service provider domain) a subscriber ID verification response message containing verified DID, DID verification result (Success or Failure), Minimum data set with subscriber/user information and Onboard Root Key ($K_{\text{ONB_Root}}$). The Onboard Root Key is otherwise called as onboard key.

8. If the UDM receives the DID verification result as 'success', it stores the received information such as verified DID, DID verification result (Success or Failure), minimum data set with user information and Onboard Root Key ($K_{\text{ONB_Root}}$) in the UDR. Otherwise if the UDM receives the DID verification result as 'failure', it stores the received information such as verified DID, DID verification result (Failure) in the UDR. If the DID verification is successful, then the UDM further generates a nonce and derives an Onboarding Security Key ($K_{\text{ONB_Sec}}$) from the received Onboard Root key using nonce as the input in key derivation as follows. The $K_{\text{ONB_Sec}}$ is used to confidentially and integrity protect the onboard container containing the User subscription information provisioned to the UE.
$$K_{\text{ONB_Sec}} = \text{KDF}(K_{\text{ONB_Root}}, \text{MNO/Service provider ID}, \text{Nonce})$$
$$K_{\text{ONB_enc}} = \text{KDF}(K_{\text{ONB_Sec}}, \text{MNO/Service provider ID}, \text{'Ciphering algorithm ID'}, \text{'DID'}, \text{keyword: 'Subscription Onboarding'})$$
$$K_{\text{ONB_int}} = \text{KDF}(K_{\text{ONB_Sec}}, \text{MNO/Service provider ID}, \text{'Ciphering algorithm ID'}, \text{'DID'}, \text{keyword: 'Subscription Onboarding'})$$
An Onboard Container shall include: K, SUPI/IMSI, AKA credentials, Security Capabilities (Authentication Method, Security Algorithm Capability), Slice Subscription Information, mobile operator public key for SUPI concealment and any other User/Service Subscription Information.
The UDM either fetches UE subscription information from a provisioning server or generates UE subscription information locally. The UDM further constructs an onboard container with the new user subscription information (K, IMSI, AKA credentials, SUCI generation inputs, Routing ID, Slice subscription information, Security information etc.) and encrypts the onboard container with the Key $K_{\text{ONB_enc}}$ and generates the MAC of the onboard container together with the onboard assistance information (OAI) IE using the integrity key $K_{\text{ONB_int}}$ to integrity protect the subscription information and related information sent to the UE. The onboard assistance information (OAI) IE can contain information on onboard result with 'success indication', security algorithms and IDs used to identify the ciphering and integrity protection algorithms used to protect the onboard container (ie., user subscription information) and related information.
9. The UDM/UDR sends the protected onboarding container with encrypted subscription information along with Nonce, OAI and MAC (Hash of onboard container || Nonce || OAI || DID || MNO/Service provider ID) to the AUSF in the Nudm_UEAuth_GetResponse message.
10. The AUSF forwards the received protected onboarding container with encrypted subscription information/plain text onboarding container along with Nonce, OAI and MAC (Hash of onboard container || Nonce || OAI || DID || MNO/Service provider ID) to the AMF in the Nudm_UEAuth_Response message.
11. The AMF sends the received protected onboarding container with encrypted subscription information along with Nonce, OAI and MAC (Hash of onboard container || Nonce || OAI || DID || MNO/Service provider ID) to the UE over the NAS transport/message in the Auth_Response message.

12. The UE on receiving the OAI with onboard result with ‘success indication’, uses the received nonce and locally available shared secret key related to the DID, to generate the onboarding security context such as $K_{\text{ONB_Root}}$, $K_{\text{ONB_Sec}}$, $K_{\text{ONB_enc}}$, $K_{\text{ONB_int}}$ Keys based on the implementation similar to the UDM/provisioning server. The UE uses $K_{\text{ONB_enc}}$ to decrypt the onboard container and uses $K_{\text{ONB_int}}$ to generate a MAC and verifies if the computed MAC is the same as the received MAC to check the integrity of the onboard container, Nonce and OAI information. If the MAC verification is successful, the UE stores the received subscription information in the trusted storage to use it for the subsequent network/service access.
The subscription information received in the onboard container can include information as follows: K, SUPI/IMSI, AKA credentials, Security Capabilities (Authentication Method, Security Algorithm Capability), Slice Subscription Information, any other User/Service Subscription Information, etc.
13. The UE can initiate a Registration Request (Initial Registration) to the AMF based on the received subscription information and a primary authentication can be performed.
14. The AMF initiates NAS SMC to set up NAS security and then AMF triggers to initiate a UE initial context set up with the gNB.
15. The gNB initiates and performs AS SMC to set up AS security context.
16. After a successful AS security set up, a protected Registration Accept message is sent to the UE.

The onboarding of IoT devices in a D2D scenario is described in the later clause 4.2.

4 AI-DRIVEN CROSS-DOMAIN SECURITY AND PRIVACY ORCHESTRATION IN IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM

4.1. Multi-domain AI-driven Orchestrator for IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum

We aim to use the UMU security orchestrator to make orchestration decisions using FL, based on a set of policies that define constraints for different services. The orchestrator must enforce these policies in the corresponding elements (network devices, NFVs, other orchestrators, etc.), translating from high/medium level policies to configuration files. In order to achieve this, orchestration algorithms and translation plugins must be defined. Orchestration algorithms will determine how the policies are enforced based on a set of inputs, while translation plugins provide different options for generating configuration files from policies.

4.1.1. Security Orchestration

The UMU security orchestrator implemented in the H2020 “INSPIRE-5Gplus” project will be leveraged in RIGOUROUS to make it driven by AI with decision making delivered across all layers of abstraction. AI-based algorithms will run fully deployed across domains and cross network-segments IoT-RAN-EDGE-Core-Cloud in the 6G network, following a Federated Learning (FL) approach to make orchestration decisions. Federated learning will be run in several execution units deployed in device-edge-cloud-continuum to improve the security orchestration capabilities to empower dynamic provisioning, deployment, and reconfiguration (during operation) of the virtual network security functions and associated intents and policies. The general structure of the orchestrator in this project is shown in Figure 29.

The 5G architecture relies on the assembly of modular systems and services that need to be both mission-aware and security-aware. To achieve this, security orchestration is essential to meet expectations, comply with policies, and adhere to regulations.

Security policy orchestration presents several challenges. One challenge pertains to defining the policies themselves. It is crucial to determine how these policies are declared and how compliant resources and services can be computed while complying with policy constraints. Another challenge is related to deploying security enforcement strategies, which involves scheduling and ensuring the availability of security functions and associated resources. Additionally, achieving interoperability and coordinating various authority perimeters is necessary to ensure global security. On the other hand, the flexibility provided by orchestration is expected to greatly benefit the deployment of intelligent protection, detection, and remediation strategies.

Policy-based security orchestration enables the orchestration of security requirements based on clearly defined security policies. This approach facilitates the management of security in intricate and diverse 5G infrastructures by standardizing the final configurations within security policies that offer multiple levels of abstraction. Furthermore, a well-defined policy-based approach notably enhances system consistency by employing various conflict detection and dependency.

Figure 29. Security Orchestrator.

The main components (services and managers) integrated and extended in the Security Orchestrator are in the framework of the INSPIRE-5Gplus project. Overall, the implementation utilizes a manager/driver system which enables the orchestrator to easily integrate new technologies by incorporating new managers and drivers into their modules.

In the rapidly evolving landscape of 5G technology, ensuring robust security mechanisms is paramount. This orchestrator plays a pivotal role in coordinating and implementing security policies across the 5G network infrastructure. Below is an overview of the primary components that contribute to this comprehensive security framework:

- **Orchestration Service**: This component serves as the starting point for coordinating and implementing security policies. In particular, it creates various classes for REST API endpoints to enforce various security policies. As an example, MSPLEnforcementService carries out the coordination and enforcement of MSPL policies with the help of dedicated MSPLOrchestrationManager and MSPLEnforcementManager. These classes carry out the particular workflow for managing and applying MSPL policies.
- **Allocation Manager**: It carries out the computation of the orchestration and enforcement strategies based on the chosen allocation type and allocation algorithms. This choice is made as the initial stage based on the features that are currently accessible. If the infrastructure supports NFV, then a NFV-enabled allocation type can be chosen as an example. If not, only conference allocation will be chosen. Additionally, a particular type of FiveGSliceAllocation has been incorporated to enforce 5G security slice policies. Different algorithms have been utilized based on load, weight, and trust in relation to the algorithms.

- **Manager of Policies:** This section puts into action various handlers for overseeing various policy structures. As the primary security policy model in INSPIRE-5GPlus is MSPL, a MSPLManager has been created. It provides ways and tools to help the orchestrator manage MSPL policies.
- **Data Service Manager:** It puts into practice a data services client that enables common access to data services. Using OpenAPI tools (swagger-codegen), auto-generated code is used to supply the appropriate data service driver.

4.2. IoT bootstrapping mechanisms

IoT device bootstrapping specification describes how the IoT devices can connect to a network for authentication and secure connection setup as well as the secure provisioning of the long-term credentials. The IoT devices are initially attaching to an onboarding network with default credentials and then retrieve their long-term credentials in form of privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials (ABC) Verifiable Credentials from a provisioning sever. The ABC credentials can be seen as a digital identity of the IoT Device that can be used for different purposes such as to authenticate itself in untrusted sub-networks or to derive proofs of its attributes that might be needed to access network applications, 6G services, and even to authenticate and access directly other previously unknown devices (as long as they also trust the Issuer) in a D2D interaction.

The onboarding procedure is built around the NANCY (An Artificial Intelligent Aided Unified Network for Secure Beyond 5G Long Term Evolution) Identity (ID), which is depicted in Figure 30:

Figure 30. NANCY Profile.

The NANCY ID has a sufficient unique length, defined by the NANCY Issuer and is bound to the UE Public Key UE_{PK} as well as a set of Attributes that define specific capabilities of the UE, holding the NANCY ID. Those attributes may be certain allowed services or access networks, i.e., 3GPP and non-3GPP type of access networks. The NANCY ID and the Attributes are signed by the NANCY Issuer, which also provides additional Credentials to access the permissioned ledger for storing the NANCY ID and UE_{PK} .

The full onboarding process is described in the following separate call flows:

- Figure 31: Initial Registration to the Onboarding Network with default credentials to gain restricted IP connectivity to the NANCY Issuer
- Figure 32: NANCY credential generation and provisioning
- Figure 33: UE DID document (NANCY ID) registration
- Figure 34: UE registration in a Serving Network with NANCY ID

Figure 31. UE Initial Registration to Onboarding Network.

The steps of Figure 31 are described in detail as follows:

1. The UE attaches to the Onboarding Network and sends a Registration Request with the Onboarding SUCI of the Default Credential Server (DCS) as UE identity to the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF).
2. The AMF detects based on the realm of the Network Access Identifier (NAI) that the Registration Request is not from a subscriber of the Network but for onboarding at a DCS. The AMF authorizes the request by verifying the realm of the NAI and whether the Network has an active agreement with this DCS. The AMF forwards the request to the AUSF which may be preconfigured for handling requests towards external DCS.
3. The AUSF may perform authorization of the registration request by verifying the realm of the NAI and whether the Network has an active agreement with this DCS. The AUSF identifies the DCS and takes the role of an Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA)-Proxy, sending a related AAA message to the corresponding AAA-Server. The AUSF sends an Authentication Request with the onboarding SUCI to the DCS. The Service Based Interface (SBI)-DIAMETER interworking functionality is collocated with the AUSF.
4. The DCS de-conceals the SUCI to a Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI) and verifies the authentication request based on the username. The DCS selects the subscriber profile based on the SUPI and performs an Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) based authentication with the UE, using the pre-shared onboarding credentials in the UE and in the DCS.
5. After successful authentication, the DCS sends the result of the authentication, the onboarding SUPI, MSK, validity time and address of the Provisioning Server back in an authentication response to the AUSF.
6. The AUSF verifies the response and derives the K_{AUSF} from the MSK and the K_{SEAF} according to 3GPP TS 33.501. the UE is performing the same key derivation accordingly.

7. The AUSF sends an authentication response to the AMF/SEAF including the authentication result from the DCS and the K_{SEAF} , the onboarding SUPI, the validity time, i.e., time until the onboarding expires and the address of the Provisioning Server.
8. The AMF performs NAS SMC with the UE.
9. After a successful NAS SMC procedure, the AMF sends the Registration Accept including the address of the Provisioning Server.
10. The UE performs a normal PDU Session Establishment procedure to gain restricted IP connectivity to the NANCY Issuer.

After the initial registration of the UE to the onboarding network, the UE has restricted IP connectivity to the NANCY Issuer and can setup an IPsec connection with a further derived key as shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32. NANCY credential generation and provisioning.

The steps of Figure 32 are described in detail as follows:

11. The UE and the DCS derive a NANCY Key K_{Pro} from the MSK in the same way.
12. The DCS provides the provisioning information Onboarding SUPI and NANCY Key K_{Pro} to the NANCY Issuer. The selection of the NANCY Issuer may be performed based on the stored address in the DCS per onboarding SUPI.
13. The UE establishes an IPsec SA with the NANCY Issuer by using the NANCY Key K_{Pro} . All messages are now confidentially and integrity protected by the IPsec tunnel.
14. The NANCY Issuer selects the Profile based on the onboarding SUPI and the corresponding Attributes.
15. The NANCY Issuer generates the Credential and signs the UE Public Key UE_{PK} and the Attributes. The NANCY Issuer assigns the NANCY ID.
16. The NANCY Issuer provisions the new NANCY profile to the UE via the IPsec tunnel.
17. The NANCY Issuer acknowledges the successful provisioning to the DCS.

18. The DCS deletes or deactivates the onboarding profile that relates to the onboarding SUPI. This prevents that if onboarding credentials are compromised, succeeding impersonation attacks from malicious UEs are prevented from being provisioned with the valid profile.

Once the UE received the NANCY document from the NANCY Issuer, the UE can write the document into the blockchain as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. UE DID document (NANCY ID) registration.

The steps of Figure 33 are described in detail as follows:

19. The UE sends a Registration Request to the Blockchain Registration node, including the provisioned certificate information for authentication and authorization to the blockchain.
20. The certificate from the UE is validated with the Blockchain Validation node.
21. After successful validation, the UE certificate is added to the allowed list to access the permissioned ledger.
22. The Blockchain Registration node acknowledges the successful registration to the blockchain towards the UE.
23. The UE sends a Write_DiD Request to the Blockchain Node, including the UE Public Key UE_{PK} . There may be further information included in the NANCY Document.
24. The Blockchain Node adds the NANCY Document to the Blockchain.
25. The Blockchain Node acknowledges the successful addition to the UE.
26. The UE is now completely provisioned and re-registers from the Onboarding Network.
27. Based on the provisioned attributes in the NANCY Profile, the UE may select a suitable access network and registers to the network.

The following call flow in Figure 34 depicts the registration to a serving network according to the attributes issued by the NANCY Issuer in step 16 of Figure 32.

Figure 34. UE registration in a Serving Network with NANCY ID.

The steps of Figure 34 are described in detail as follows:

1. The UE sends a NAS Registration Request to the AMF, indicating that it wants to connect with NANCY credentials. The UE may include an anonymous SUCI (e.g., anonymous@operator.xy) with the NAI of the network.
2. The AMF replies with a NAS Response and the presentation policy for registering to the network with NANCY credentials. The policy may require the UE to construct the presentation token in a specific way and to include specific attributes which are important for the mobile network operator. Those required attributes may be but not limited to: encrypted SUPI, encrypted Root Key, NANCY Issuer Public Key, Revocation parameters, requested services (IP connectivity, IMS Services, etc.), QoS profile etc.,
3. The UE will create a presentation token according to the policy. The UE may include a proof that it holds the private key corresponding to the pseudonym used in the presentation token.
4. The UE sends a NAS request to the AMF including the presentation token.
5. The AMF checks the validity of the presentation token. This is done by verifying the signatures of the attributes signed by the NANCY Issuer with the public key of the Issuer K_{Puplss} . The AMF may also check the proof of the private key of the UE with the pseudonym in the credentials. The AMF checks the attributes containing revocation information signed by the NANCY Issuer, or may involve the Revocation Authority for the check, whether the credential is still active and potentially additional information about the service, e.g., remaining data volume, remaining time etc.
6. If the credential is not revoked, the AMF/SEAF sends a Nausf_UEAuthentication_Authenticate Request message to the AUSF including the presentation token. Alternative the AMF/SEAF may only include the encrypted attributes related to the root key and the subscription identity.

7. The AUSF queries the Issuer with a Reveal Attribute Request message, including the presentation token or alternatively only the encrypted attributes related to the root key and the subscription identity. This message may be sent via the NEF.
8. The NANCY Issuer verifies the request and the presentation token or the encrypted attributes. The Issuer also verifies the signature and decrypts the encrypted attributes, i.e., at least Root Key KRoot and subscription identity SUPI. The NANCY Issuer sends a Reveal Attribute Response message to the AUSF including the decrypted attributes, i.e., at least the Root Key KRoot and subscription identity SUPI.
9. The AUSF does not query the UDM and selects the authentication method. EAP-AKA' would be most suitable depending on whether the user purchased NANCY credential access with non-3GPP networks and uses the NANCY credential access also on devices not supporting the NAS protocol. There is further no need to query the UDM, since the user is not a subscriber of the mobile operators, thus does not have a record in the UDM and the Issuer is taking care of decryption of the Root Key and the SUPI. The AUSF creates an authentication challenge as per normal operation and specified in 3GPP TS 33.501.
10. The AUSF sends a Nausf_UEAuthentication_Authenticate Response to the AMF/SEAF including the authentication challenge.
11. The AMF/SEAF sends the authentication challenge to the UE in a NAS message. The AMF/SEAF includes a Presentation Token Success indication in the NAS Message.
12. The UE selects the Root Key KRoot and the SUPI for this mobile network according to the credential previously issued from the Issuer. If KRoot and SUPI were encrypted in the credential with the pseudonym of the UE, then the UE decrypts the KRoot and SUPI with its private key KUPr. The UE computes the authentication result from the authentication challenge as per normal operation specified in TS 33.501.
13. The UE completes the authentication procedure as per normal operation and AUSF and UE derive the keys accordingly.
14. The AMF/SEAF perform the NAS Security Mode Command procedure as per normal operation.
15. After the all-security procedures are completed, the AMF sends a NAS Registration Accept message to the UE including the 5G-GUTI. The UE will use the 5G-GUTI as in normal operation for further requests.

The UE could now setup a PDU Session according to the normal procedures to gain IP connectivity in the serving network.

4.3 Trusted application onboarding

Application exposes how it handles data, especially private data. This information can be used to have multiple versions of the same application with different operational characteristics, or to have different applications providing the same function, but with different privacy characteristics. The set of services can be different, as the network applications providing less privacy may be able to provide additional integrations or the capability to further enhance its services.

In the call flow in Figure 35, the UE is provisioned with the fingerprint of the genuine application developer certificates for a specific application, identified with its application ID. The previously

received credential from the NANCY Issuer also contains an attribute of the applications the respective network wants to manage with URSP rules. This attribute is protected with the Issuer public key to prevent knowledge on the managed applications. Another attribute part of the credential is containing the Certified Application Server (CAS) address, the CAS is responsible for assembling the corresponding list of application ID and certificate fingerprint pairs as well as encrypting them with the UEs public key.

Figure 35. Trusted application onboarding with NANCY ID.

The steps of Figure 35 are described in detail as follows:

1. As a prerequisite, the UE is registered in the serving network using the NANCY ID as described in the clause 4.2 and has IP connectivity. The Certified Application Server is holding the pairs of unique application ID per operating system and the corresponding fingerprint of the application developer certificate. The CAS can retrieve the fingerprint of the application developer certificate from the respective trusted application store e.g., from the operation system provider.
2. The UE is sending a Certified Application Request message with a NANCY ID indication to the CAS. The UE retrieves the CAS address in the credential issued by the NANCY Issuer for a specific network access.
3. The CAS sends a Certified Application Response message with a NANCY presentation policy requesting the presence of the Application ID attribute.
4. The UE generates the presentation token according to the NANCY presentation policy from the CAS. The UE may include a proof that it holds the private key corresponding to the pseudonym used in the presentation token.
5. The UE sends a new Certified Application Request to the CAS including the presentation token.
6. The CAS checks the validity of the presentation token. This is done by verifying the signatures of the attributes signed by the Issuer with the public key of the Issuer K_{PubIss} . The CAS may also check the proof of the private key of the UE with the pseudonym in the credentials. The CAS

checks the attributes containing revocation information signed by the Issuer, or may involve the Revocation Authority for the check, whether the credential is still active.

7. If the credential is not revoked, the CAS queries the Issuer with a Reveal Attribute Request message, including the presentation token or alternatively only the encrypted attributes related to the Application IDs.

8. The Issuer verifies the request and the presentation token or the encrypted attributes. The Issuer also verifies the signature and decrypts the encrypted attributes, i.e., at least the Application IDs that are managed by the serving network. The Issuer sends a Reveal Attribute Response message to the CAS including the decrypted attributes, i.e., at least the list of the Application IDs.

9. The CAS selects the certificate fingerprints for the requests App IDs and encrypts the App ID - certificate fingerprint pairs with the UE public key. The CAS may sign the message with its private key.

10. The CAS sends a new Certified Application Response message with the NANCY presentation policy success indication and the encrypted list of App ID - certificate fingerprint pairs.

11. The UE checks the validity of the message by verifying the signature of the CAS and decrypts the list of the App ID - certificate fingerprint pairs. The UE installs the list for future verification of already installed applications matching the application ID or future installations of those applications.

12. If an application is installed with the same application ID matching one of the received list from the CAS, then the UE validates the fingerprint of the embedded developer certificate of the installed application with the one received from the CAS and if identical, the application is considered as genuine. If not identical, then the UE shall remove the application from the device. If the serving network provided URSP rules to manage the traffic of specific applications identified with the application ID, then the UE verifies that only genuine applications are allowed to match a URSP rule by verifying the certificate fingerprints at the time when an application with a certain application ID requests to send data.

5 ZERO TRUST AND SMART SECURITY MANAGEMENT

5.1. Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework for the B5G and 6G system

We aim to develop a standalone system for trust score evaluation and assignment based on the collection of abnormal behaviour(s) specific event data e.g., violation data from as well as statistics from the entities involved (UEs, RAN, Core NFs, AFs etc.). Utilizing these trust scores, the network and management domain entities can make decisions during the network operation and orchestration to mitigate risks and threats in the network. The trust score assignment follows three major steps: Data Collection, abnormal behaviour event i.e., violation translation and trust score assignment by the trust evaluation and trust enabler (TESF). Furthermore, the TESP service can trigger the AI driven decision engine to act reactively if major trust-based violation is identified in the network. In this section, we describe the system design of the TESP, the technologies and procedures used, the types and nature of attacks that we have considered along with some initial results of unit tests for the standalone TESP realization.

5.1.1. Prototype Design

The technology enablers required for the prototype configuration and deployment are:

UERANSIM for UE and gNB: The User Equipment's (UE(s)) and Next Generation Node B (gNB) is simulated using UERANSIM where the UEs can register themselves with the core network through the gNB and establish unique PDU sessions. UERANSIM allows to simulate multiple UEs connected to single or multiple gNB(s). The UE and gNB interact with the 5G core through the N1 and N2 interface respectively.

Open5gs for the 5G Core: An open-source implementation using C language contains a series of software components and network functions that implement the 5G SA core functions. The Open5GS 5G SA Core contains the following functions:

- NRF - NF Repository Function
- SCP - Service Communication Proxy
- SEPP - Security Edge Protection Proxy
- AMF - Access and Mobility Management Function
- SMF - Session Management Function
- UPF - User Plane Function
- AUSF - Authentication Server Function
- UDM - Unified Data Management
- UDR - Unified Data Repository
- PCF - Policy and Charging Function
- NSSF - Network Slice Selection Function
- BSF - Binding Support Function

The 5G SA core uses a Service Based Architecture (SBA). Control plane functions are configured to register with the NRF, and the NRF then helps them discover the other core functions.

Prometheus and Alert manager for alert generation: Prometheus is a monitoring tool that can be used to generate custom alerts and the alert manager can be utilized to trigger alerts in case the rule applies in a certain state of the nodes involved in monitoring.

Flask Server for the TESH: The Flask Server acts as the deployment base for the TESH where the alert manager can send data based on violation and the processor can take decisions and send responses to other entities in the network.

FastAPI for Rest API based communication: FastAPI is a modern web framework for building RESTful APIs in Python. It was first released in 2018 and has since quickly gained popularity among developers due to its ease of use, speed and robustness.

Figure 36. Prototype design of Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service function.

As in the Figure 36, the UEs and gNB namely the simulated RAN is connected to the core network Open5gs where the network functions (NFs) such as AMF, SMF, PCF etc. interact through the service based interface. These NFs have Prometheus clients which can potentially measure metrics (like number of active gNBs and UE, successful and rejected registration requests etc.) from the NFs and their interactions with the other components in the network. The Prometheus server can fetch data from these Prometheus clients and based on predefined rules, can forward any violation to the alertmanager. The alertmanager can trigger context with violation data on the interface connected like a webhook, the entry point of the TESH in this case. On receiving violation data, the processor associated with the TESH verifies the logs of the affected network function and results in the extent of the violation as well as the source of the violation (or the source of the attack). With this violation data as well as the attack source, the trust manager assigns a trust score to the source of the violation based on a trust algorithm. These trust scores are stored in the database and are available to the external management domain entities like the Security

Orchestrator through a REST interface. The Trust Manager also enables triggering the Decision Engine in events of major violation (like when the trust score of a network component is below a minimum threshold) through a publish-subscribe broker like Kafka. Furthermore, the TESP shown here as a separate entity can also be a part of the core network itself.

Figure 37. Joint Histogram of the distribution of AMF CPU percentage under the influence of attack (red) and in normal state (blue). Measured for 5.5 mins in linuxenv.

Threat Model and Attack Scenario:

Aligned to the goal of the TESP which aims to record and report violation; and assign trust score to the source of the violation (the attacker), it is important to formulate attacks that impact the core network functions from outside the core network (UE and RAN) as well as within the Core Network (compromised NFs). Hence as an attack from outside the core, we formulate an attack i.e., DOS attack from the UE where registered UEs perform redundant registrations leading to congestion in the network as well as resource exhaustion at AMF in the core network. The Figure 37 presents the influence of the DOS attack on the AMF CPU in the form of a histogram. The red color indicates the estimates of the CPU usage under the attack scenario while the blue indicates in normal condition. Clearly the effectiveness of the attack can be observed leading to disruption of the AMF functionalities as well as AMF crash in worst cases. The message flow diagram was

reported in the deliverable D3.1 as the component design, here the information flow can be represented as in the Figure 38.

Figure 38. Attack Scenario and workflow of the ZTM.

5.1.2. Preliminary Results

In this section, we test the components developed using unit test like scenarios to check the correctness of the actions taken by the TESP as a part of Zero Trust Management. In doing so, we will define the logic and steps chronologically with screenshots of the working prototype.

Subscriber Creation in Open5gs WebGUI and Attack generation:

We create a total of 10 subscriber for UEs with IMSI from 99900000000001 to 99900000000010. In the first phase, all 10 UEs perform a registration to the core network. Next, out of the 10 UEs 5 of them are malicious and run a Python script that starts the re-registration attack.

Prometheus firing rule and Alertmanager trigger:

We define the rule at the Prometheus as shown in Figure 39 below:

```

/etc/prometheus/rules_UE.yml > example
  
```

▼ UeConfUpdateExceed (1 active)

```

name: UeConfUpdateExceed
expr: fivegs_amffunction_mm_confupdate > amf_session
for: 2s
  
```

Figure 39. Prometheus Rules.

The number of AMF sessions are unique for the UEs but the `conf_update` is incremented with every extra registration (in the attacks scenario). As the firing from the Prometheus occurs, the alertmanager is updated for generation of triggers to the webhook which is connected to the TESP as show in the Figure 40 below:

Figure 40. Action of the Alert Manager.

Trust Manager Invocation and Trust Score Generation

As the trust manager receives the JSON file with the alert details, it checks the AMF logs for the UEs which are potentially the attacker(s). We use a simple algorithm in this case as:

```
ENTER AMF LOGS:  
  WHILE TIME < TIME_THRESHOLD:  
    CHECK FOR AMF CONFUPDATE:  
      STORE THE UE IMSI AND INCREMENT (RECORD VIOLATION).  
  FOR EVERY VIOLATION OF UE:  
    UPDATE TRUST SCORE  
RETURN UE_IMSI, TRUST SCORE
```

The task manager as the Flask server penalizes the UEs inducing the attacks by reducing their trust score and identifies which AMF has been affected, as shown in Figure 41:

```
souvik@5GlnaBox:~/Desktop/TESEF$ sudo .venv/bin/python3
python3 python3.10
souvik@5GlnaBox:~/Desktop/TESEF$ sudo .venv/bin/python3 ./server.py
[sudo] password for souvik:
* Serving Flask app 'server'
* Debug mode: on
WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment. Use a production WSGI server instead.
* Running on all addresses (0.0.0.0)
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:5004
* Running on http://10.0.2.15:5004
Press CTRL+C to quit
* Restarting with stat
* Debugger is active!
* Debugger PIN: 129-984-515
json file received
127.0.0.1 - - [08/Mar/2024 00:48:04] "POST /prometheus HTTP/1.1" 200 -
json file received
03/08 00:46:53.888: [amf] INFO: [imsi-999700000000001] Configuration update command (./src/amf/nas-path.c:612)
Trust score reduction algorithm initialted for UE with IMSI 999700000000001 associated with AMF: 127.0.0.5:9091
03/08 00:48:20.446: [amf] INFO: [imsi-999700000000002] Configuration update command (./src/amf/nas-path.c:612)
Trust score reduction algorithm initialted for UE with IMSI 999700000000002 associated with AMF: 127.0.0.5:9091
03/08 00:48:20.446: [amf] INFO: [imsi-999700000000001] Configuration update command (./src/amf/nas-path.c:612)
Trust score reduction algorithm initialted for UE with IMSI 999700000000001 associated with AMF: 127.0.0.5:9091
```

Figure 41. TESF Server response to attacks.

As this algorithm finishes execution, we check for the trust score of a single attacker UE and get the data as shown in Figure 42:

```
{
  "type": "bundle",
  "id": "bundle--574093e8-65fe-4128-a737-3db32a7a8558",
  "objects": [
    {
      "type": "anomalies",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "anomalies--ef158812-748e-468f-b8d3-ab628f7a23bc",
      "created": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.826588+00:00",
      "modified": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.826588+00:00",
      "error_type": "re-registration",
      "ip": "999700000000001",
      "trust_score": 80,
      "revoked": false
    },
    {
      "type": "networkentity",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "networkentity--9ff351b9-396e-4ca7-8beb-4f84af40dce4",
      "created": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.827187+00:00",
      "modified": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.827187+00:00",
      "name": "amf",
      "ip": "127.0.0.5",
      "revoked": false
    },
    {
      "type": "relationship",
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "id": "relationship--cd3d60e5-57c8-4a8b-8d56-d2349c1be8cb",
      "created": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.827597+00:00",
      "modified": "2024-05-30T23:18:28.827597+00:00",
      "relationship_type": "indicates",
      "source_ref": "anomalies--ef158812-748e-468f-b8d3-ab628f7a23bc",
      "target_ref": "networkentity--9ff351b9-396e-4ca7-8beb-4f84af40dce4",
      "revoked": false
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 42. STIX data format for reporting trust scores.

6 END-TO-END MULTIDOMAIN MULTI-TENANT 6G SLICING

6.1. Security Agents and Security Slice Controllers for End-to-end multi-domain slicing

In order to achieve security in network slices between different domains, security agents and slice controllers must be deployed in the scenario. Security agents are in charge of monitoring and managing the network elements, obtaining data from the devices that can be used to make security decisions, and applying security enforcements from orchestrators. Security slice controllers generate and enforce channel protection policies for network slices from the security orchestrator.

6.1.1. Orchestration of channel-protected security slices

Channel-protected security slices combine filtering policies and IPsec channel protection policies in order to provide end-to-end security for devices in two different levels: by limiting the traffic through the filtering policies, and to protect messages by creating IPsec tunnels between the components. The Security Orchestrator is able to generate and deploy channel-protected security slice configuration files in SDN controllers (with help from the Intent Security Manager) from MSPL policies received from the Decision Engine. In a multi-domain environment, each SDN controller must deploy the filtering and IPsec configuration to the involved devices. Figure 43 shows the architecture of a multi-domain scenario with channel-protected security slices.

Figure 43. Orchestration of channel-protected security slices.

6.1.2. Security slices based on IPsec for channel protection

The IPsec (Internet Protocol Security) is a well-known and widely used security protocol over IPv4 and IPv6 networks. It provides confidentiality, integrity and authentication to the network traffic over IP. However, it requires the configuration of every device with a set of policies (stored internally in the SPD or Security Policy Database) that determine which traffic flows must be protected, and a set of associations (stored in the SAD or Security Association Database) containing all the required information to process the traffic, such as cryptographic keys, algorithms, or initialization vectors.

The most common way to negotiate and exchange this information is through the Internet Key Exchange (IKEv2) protocol, which was designed for this purpose. In order to provide a secure way for devices to generate a shared secret for encryption (and/or integrity), IKEv2 uses a set of message exchanges, that can change in number in some scenarios. The first exchange, denoted as IKE_SA_INIT, negotiate the cryptographic algorithms that will be used to protect the packets. It also performs a Diffie-Hellman exchange (involving the creation of a public and private key-pair in each device, and exchanging only the public keys), which will be used to create the shared secret. Nonces are also exchanged, to provide an additional point of randomness to the symmetric key derivation. The second exchange, named IKE_AUTH, provides authentication to the previous (and future) messages, by sending identities and certificates. Additionally, an IPsec security association (SA) is created in this exchange, named Child SA, in order to protect the next messages and avoid attackers peeking sensitive information. After these two initial exchanges, the following messages

are encrypted (using the SA created in IKE_AUTH) and their integrity protected using the algorithms negotiated in IKE_SA_INIT. Now, each device is able to derive keys for integrity and encryption using the Child SA in IKE_SA_INIT in a process named SKEYSEED. Any device may start a CREATE_CHILD_SA exchange to create IPsec SAs to protect traffic between these devices. After a process of mutual authentication using identities or certificates, a set of parameters are exchanged, more specifically: a SA offer, a nonce value, optionally a new Diffie-Hellman public key (to ask for a new Diffie-Hellman key generation in the other device), and traffic selectors (that are used to filter the traffic that needs to be secured with the generated SA). The other device will respond with its correspondent parameters, and if no errors occurred, both devices will have created functional IPsec SAs to protect their traffic.

IPsec SAs are used to protect IP packets only in one direction between two devices (inbound or outbound), thus bidirectional secure communication will need at least two SAs in each device. The information stored in the outbound SA for a device sending data must be the same as the inbound SA for the device receiving data, as the same cryptographic material and algorithms need to be used for ciphering and deciphering packets.

Thanks to the centralization of the SDN paradigm, we can take advantage of the SDN controller to automatically create and deploy IPsec tunnels, which can be done proactively (for instance, as soon as a new device is connected in the network) or reactively (on demand, only when a device needs to securely communicate with another). The SDN controller supports both working modes, and can be configured to use any of them. Additionally, the SDN controller and the software running in the devices have been designed to be able to drop off the use of the IKEv2 protocol for the IPsec key negotiation and exchange, and instead leverage the SDN controller, which communicates with the nodes in a secure way, and use it to generate and distribute IPsec material to devices (IKE-less approach). The idea of replacing the use of IKEv2 for the SDN controller resides in the inherent complexity overhead of using IKEv2. Even though currently there are routers and switches that support IKEv2, they are more expensive and complex. Moreover, most energy and memory constrained devices, such as IoT, are not compatible with IKEv2 due to this extra complexity and power needed to perform the IPsec negotiations. For these reasons, this SDN architecture uses the controller for distributing IPsec material and provides support for more devices. Potentially it could be able to perform better than using IKEv2, as it avoids the overheads of the IKEv2 exchanges. Nevertheless, the controller and the devices support both working modes: with and without IKEv2.

After receiving a MSPL policy for security slicing using IPsec, the Security Orchestrator uses the Intent-based Security Management component to process the policy and extract the information needed to translate it into a configuration message for the SDN controller, which is the target enabler in charge of communicating with the devices that will be protected through the channel protection policies. The SDN controller will process the IPsec configuration and deploy SPD and SAD entries into the correspondent devices through the southbound API, which will be able to create IPsec tunnels between them after this deployment.

The SDN controller, after receiving a message from the Security Orchestrator, processes it and starts to communicate with its devices. Proactive and reactive working modes are only available for the IKE-less approach, and the configuration files and overall processes are very similar to the

IKEv2 approach, so we will focus on the IKE-less version of the scenario. In the proactive mode, the controller will create the IPsec parameters and send them to the devices as soon as it receives the configuration message from the Security Orchestrator. Devices are configured with a custom software for the communication with the controller, and which will create SPD and SAD entries directly in the kernel using the XFRM framework. In the reactive mode, the controller installs SPD entries in the devices, so they will check if the traffic must be protected before sending it. If they need protection and there is no SAD entry for the traffic, they send an ACQUIRE notification to the controller, which will create and distribute the SAD entries to the corresponding devices. Figure 44 presents the configuration message the controller sends to a device with the SPD entry parameters. The XML showed serves as a template for the controller, so all placeholders are replaced later with actual values obtained from the Security Orchestrator configuration messages. Usually, three SPD entries are sent in the same message to each device: one for incoming traffic (inbound), other for outgoing traffic (outbound), and another for forwarded traffic (forwarding). As these entries are very similar, only the inbound traffic one is showed in Figure 44. Something similar happens to SAD entries, as depicted in Figure 45. For bidirectional communication, two SAD entries are carried out: one for inbound traffic, and another for outbound. Again, placeholder values are replaced with actual values from the Security Orchestrator.

In order to obtain some results about the performance, the time needed to complete the SAD and SPD installation has been measured. In this preliminary tests, only the time from the controller sending the SPD and SAD messages until their replies with OKs after the installation has been measured, so in future tests other elements in the scenario can be taken into account (for instance, the time needed to generate and send MSPL policies from the decision engine to the Security Orchestrator, the time needed to process the policies and create configuration messages, etc.).

```
<config xmlns="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:netconf:base:1.0">
  <ietf-ipsec xmlns="http://example.net/ietf-ipsec" xmlns:nc="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:netconf:base:1.0">
    <ipsec>
      <spd>
        <spd-entry>
          <rule-number>RULE_IN</rule-number>
          <priority>0</priority>
          <names>
            <name>in/REMOTE_ADDRESS/32/LOCAL_ADDRESS/32</name>
          </names>
          <condition>
            <traffic-selector-list>
              <ts-number>102</ts-number>
              <direction>INBOUND</direction>
              <local-addresses>
                <start>REMOTE_ADDRESS/32</start>
                <end>REMOTE_ADDRESS/32</end>
              </local-addresses>
              <remote-addresses>
                <start>LOCAL_ADDRESS/32</start>
                <end>LOCAL_ADDRESS/32</end>
              </remote-addresses>
              <next-layer-protocol>TCP</next-layer-protocol>
              <local-ports>
                <start>0</start>
                <end>0</end>
              </local-ports>
              <remote-ports>
                <start>0</start>
                <end>0</end>
              </remote-ports>
            </traffic-selector-list>
          </condition>
          <processing-info>
            <action>PROTECT</action>
            <ipsec-sa-cfg>
              <security-protocol>esp</security-protocol>
              <mode>MODE_TYPE</mode>
            </ipsec-sa-cfg>
          </processing-info>
        </spd-entry>
      </spd>
    </ipsec>
  </ietf-ipsec>
</config>
```

Figure 44. SPD configuration message from controller to device.

These tests have been made in all the controller's working modes: IKE-less proactive, IKE-less reactive, and IKE case, so we can compare their performance. Additionally, we have tried to enforce a high number of configuration messages in the SDN controller, to check its resilience and its behavior under pressure, so we have created a mesh scenario with a variable number of devices, from 2 to 30, and we created IPsec tunnels between all of them at the same time in each scenario.

```
<sad>
  <sad-entry>
    <spi>SPI_IN</spi> <!-- SPIa1=SPI1 in A-->
    <anti-replay-window>ANTI_REPLAY_WINDOW</anti-replay-window>
    <rule-number>0</rule-number>
    <local-addresses>
      <start>REMOTE_ADDRESS/32</start>
      <end>REMOTE_ADDRESS/32</end>
    </local-addresses>
    <remote-addresses>
      <start>LOCAL_ADDRESS/32</start>
      <end>LOCAL_ADDRESS/32</end>
    </remote-addresses>
    <next-layer-protocol>TCP</next-layer-protocol>
    <local-ports>
      <start>0</start>
      <end>0</end>
    </local-ports>
    <remote-ports>
      <start>0</start>
      <end>0</end>
    </remote-ports>
    <security-protocol>esp</security-protocol>
    <esp-sa>
      <encryption>
        <encryption-algorithm>ENCRYPTION_ALGORITHM</encryption-algorithm>
        <key>ENC_KEY_VALUE_1</key>
        <iv>ENC_IV</iv>
      </encryption>
      <integrity>
        <integrity-algorithm>INTEGRITY_ALGORITHM</integrity-algorithm>
        <key>INT_KEY_VALUE_1</key>
      </integrity>
    </esp-sa>
    <mode>MODE_TYPE</mode>
    <sad-lifetime-soft>
      <bytes>SOFT_BYTES</bytes>
      <packets>SOFT_PACKETS</packets>
      <added>SOFT_ADDED</added>
      <used>SOFT_USED</used>
    </sad-lifetime-soft>
    <sad-lifetime-hard>
      <bytes>HARD_BYTES</bytes>
      <packets>HARD_PACKETS</packets>
      <added>HARD_ADDED</added>
      <used>HARD_USED</used>
    </sad-lifetime-hard>
  </sad-entry>
</sad>
```

Figure 45. SAD configuration message from controller to device.

Figure 46 shows a graphic with the results, and we can see that the IKE case provides the best performance, as the key exchange has been extremely optimized, while the IKE-less case with reactive mode taking into account the two configuration stages (SPD installation and SAD installation) take the most amount of time. As these tests show the worst scenario, in which the

controller would have to process all the tunnels at the same time, we can use instead the IKE-less proactive mode, which provides better results.

Figure 46. Time results for the installation of IPsec tunnels using different working modes of the SDN controller.

In a typical scenario, in which the IPsec installations are spread in the time, the IKE-less reactive mode works better than the IKE-less proactive mode, as the controller needs less time to generate and deploy only the SPD entries, and the workload descends as it does not need to install the SAD entries right after. Even though the IKE case provides better results, we only measured the IKEv2 configuration time, and we have not taken into account the time needed for negotiation. It is also notable that even if the IKE-less approaches have a lower performance compared to the IKE case, the former provides the devices all the information needed to create the IPsec tunnels, and there is no need to perform any later negotiation between them.

6.1.3. Slice Manager

This subsection presents a first functional prototype of the Slice Manager (SM) RIGOROUS architectural component. The SM is responsible for delivering End-to-End (E2E) network slicing capabilities in multi-tenant and multi-domain 5G/6G infrastructures. A key target of the RIGOROUS project is to provide an adaptive, interoperable and flexible E2E network slicing architecture as a suitable solution for multi-tenant multi-domain 6G deployments. To do so, it is

required to provide a slicing control solution able to handle the different programmable network devices and technologies comprising the data plane. Then, network slicing will be used as a mitigation technique to isolate the harmful traffic from a cyber-attack in a low-priority low-bandwidth disadvantaged slice and, thus protecting the legitimate users' traffic, services and 6G infrastructure itself.

As presented in deliverable D3.1, the first prototype of the SM consists of three main sub-components whose functionality and implementation details are explained as follows:

- **SM NBI (API REST):** The Slice Manager exposes a North-Bound Interface (NBI) to the UMU orchestrator using an REST API. This API is called by the UMU orchestrator when a network slice either has to be created or deleted in the data plane or a data flow (i.e. malicious traffic from an attacker) has to be attached to an existing slice. The communication between the UMU orchestrator and the SM is done using JSON messages.
- **E2E Slice Engine:** The main task of the E2E Slice Engine is to handle the network slices that are enforced at a given time in the data plane, providing the upper layers (i.e. orchestrator) with such slicing capabilities. To achieve this, the Slice Engine sub-component relies on the topological network information provided by the Topology Inventory Agent (described as part of WP4) which allows the SM to have a comprehensive vision of the network topology. This topological information allows the SM to take an efficient decision related to where in the network the slice will be enforced to ensure an E2E deployment. The SE sends to the different Security Control Agents (SCAs) deployed across the infrastructure a *"technology-agnostic slice definition"* message with the information needed to create a slice, delete a slice or attach a network flow to a particular slice.
- **Security Control Agent (SCA):** The SCA is the South-Bound Interface of the SM. The SCA is a distributed component deployed in all infrastructure nodes where a network slice could be deployed. Through a common unified API, it provides programmability capabilities for different underlying technologies and network interfaces composing the data plane, in particular, all needed functionalities related to life-cycle of a network slice. Hence, the SCA provides the SM with a data plane abstraction to hide the network complexity to upper layers while using a specific slicing enabler, i.e. the Network Self-Protection component. So, the SCA agents translate the *"technology-agnostic slice definition"* message from the E2E Slice Engine into a *"technology-dependent slice enforcement"* set of actions that will result in the execution at data plane level of the slice action required (creation, deletion, or flow attaching).

Figure 47 shows the message interchange between the UMU orchestrator and the Slice Manager and the internal communication between the E2E Slice Engine and the SCAs instances deployed across the infrastructure for the creation of a network slice. As stated above, both communications are based on JSON format messages. As can be observed in Figure 47, to create a network slice, the UMU orchestrator sends a *"Slice Definition"* message to the Slice Manager. This message contains the slice name (*"sliceName"*), the QoS parameters of the slice

("maxBandwidth", "minBandwidth", and "priority"), and a list of network points (network interfaces) where the slice will be enforced ("resources").

The Slice Manager uses the information in the "Slice Definition" message and the topological information provided by the RIA and kept in the *Topology Database* to take a decision on where to enforce the slice in the data plane. Then, the SM sends a "technology-agnostic slice definition" message to the SCAs instances distributed through the 6G infrastructure. The SCA provides the E2E Slice Engine and the upper management and control layer with an abstraction layer of the data plane allowing an enhanced and flexible programmability. As an example, Figure 47 shows an excerpt of one "technology-agnostic slice definition" JSON message which contains, among other, the following information:

- Host where the network slice will be instantiated ("deviceHostName")
- Network interface in the host where the slice will be attached ("iface")
- Slice enabler ("programmableTechnology")
- Interface status reported by RIA ("state", "devicePortSpeed", "currentTXQueues")
- QoS parameters of the slice ("minbandwidth", "maxbandwidth", "priority")
- Traffic sense of the slice. It could be uplink or downlink ("sense")
- Unique slice ID ("sliceName")
- Action timestamps

Figure 47. Slice Manager architecture and JSON messages for network slice creation.

In the example in Figure 47, this slice enabler is the RIGOUROUS Network Self-Protection asset ("*programmableTechnology*" in the JSON intent-based message).

After creating a slice, the malicious flows detected need to be attached to a slice for the purpose of mitigating a cyber-attack and securing the infrastructure. The exchange of messages is similar to the one explained above for the creation of a slice, but in this case the JSON messages contain information about the malicious flows and the slice ID to be attached to. Figure 48 shows an excerpt of the JSON messages sent by the orchestrator and the E2E Slice Engine sub-component to attach a flow to a specific network slice.

Figure 48. Slice Manager architecture and JSON messages for flow attachment.

The JSON message sent by the orchestrator contains all the information related to the concrete selection of the malicious flow in the data plane, for example, source and destination IP addresses and ports, any encapsulation information, the sense of the flow in the data plane (INGRESS or EGRESS), and type of traffic (e.g. TCP, OVS, IP). The same JSON message contains as well the "sliceld" where the flow needs to be attached. This information is being used by the SCAs to perform the concrete slice enforcement into the data plane.

6.1.4. Network Self-Protection

This subsection presents a first functional prototype of the Network Self Protection (NSP), a software-based network slicing enabler agent suitable for 5G/6G multi-tenant networks deployed in the Data Plane (DP). Hence, technical details of design, architectural sub-components, functionalities, and implementation aspects as well as preliminary empirical results are provided in the following.

The purpose of this RIGOUROUS asset is to deliver enhanced data plane programmability enabling fine-grained control over network traffic across the virtualized networks in the Edge and Core segments, in particular in 5G/6G multi-tenant infrastructures. The NSP provides a novel mechanism with enough maturity level to be suitable against cyber incidents compromising the infrastructure.

6.1.4.1. Background

The proposed implementation of the NSP is based on the well-known software virtual Switch OVS [5], which has become a *de facto* standard in data centers and cloud deployments. The NSP design follows the Software Defined Network (SDN) approach where control and forwarding network capabilities are decoupled [9]. SDN technology offers a centralized vision of the network topology and status, providing the management and control layers with centralized control and flexible and dynamic network programmability. In addition, adopting SDN combined with virtualization and softwarization technologies such as NFV or Network Slicing allows the use of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) hardware instead of expensive and dedicated equipment and network devices traditionally deployed in infrastructures such as mobile operator, data centers and cloud providers. COTS equipment is significantly cheaper than dedicated hardware, resulting in a substantial reduction of Operational Expenditure (OPEX) and Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) costs for infrastructure owners.

With regards to control protocols, Open Flow (OF) [9] is the most widely used protocol to enable SDN capabilities. OF is actively maintained by the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) and the latest released version is OpenFlow 1.5 (code 0x06). Many network switch and router vendors support OF. Indeed, there are many examples of SDN controllers with Open Flow support such as OpenDayLight [9], Neutron [10] or ONOS [11] just to list a few of the most popular ones.

Another relevant aspect to consider is the kind of traffic expected in 5G/6G multi-tenant networks, i.e., network traffic with multiple levels of nested encapsulation using protocols such as GTP to guarantee user mobility or VXLAN, GRE or GENEVE to provide isolation between tenants (see Figure 49). Traditional QoS mechanisms and traffic classifiers have scalability, programmability and flexibility limitations that make them ineffective for multi-tenant networks. Moreover, traditional traffic classifiers mapping outer L3/L4 values in a 5-tuple lack enough expressiveness to provide the fine-grained classification capabilities required in multi-tenant 5G/6G networks, where tenant, user, and service information is conveyed in the inner encapsulated headers of the network packets.

Figure 49. Different types of traffic in multi-tenant overlay networks as a consequence of the encapsulation/decapsulation process: IP, LTE traffic and 5G/6G multi-tenant traffic.

The NSP component aims to deliver network slicing capabilities as cyber-attack mitigation technique in all involved segments carrying softwarized VNFs, to be more precise the software data path in the Edge and Core segments in charge of interconnecting the VNFs to the physical network. After a comparative analysis of the state of the art of existing Software Data Path solutions such as eXpress Data Path (XDP), Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) or OpenVSwitch, OVS has been selected as baseline for the implementation of the NSP RIGOUROUS asset. The key reasons supporting this decision are the following:

- OVS is a well-known software switch widely deployed in virtualized and SDN environments where it is considered the *de facto* standard.
- OVS is an open-source SDN Software Switch in constant development and supported by a wide developer community.
- It offers an NBI based on OF which can be extended to enable enhanced data plane programmability.
- It is widely adopted by frameworks and cloud management tools such as OpenStack [12].
- Proven efficient and satisfactory performance and robustness.

6.1.4.2. Architectural design

Figure 50 depicts the architectural design of the NSP RIGOUROUS network slicing enabler. The NSP is a software flow agent providing advanced traffic classification and control features for a specific segment of the 5G and beyond multi-tenant networks: the software data path segment. This

network segment plays a key role in virtualized environments since it is in charge of connecting the different virtualized networks of the different tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure. The NSP is composed of 6 sub-components which cooperate together to provide fine-grained control and network slicing features, thus offering a new mechanism for cyber-attack mitigation based on network slicing. A brief functional description of each of the logical sub-components is given as follows:

- **OpenFlow North Bound Interface:** Enables the communication between the Slice Manager in the Control Plane and the Software Data Plane. For this purpose, it exposes an Open Flow API. The Open Flow protocol has been significantly extended, adding new fields and actions to enrich the expressiveness of the predicate of the OF rules allowing a more flexible and granular data flows definition able to cope with all expected data paths in 5G/6G multi-tenant networks.
- **5G/6G Multi-tenant Traffic Classifier:** It is the ingress point into the NSP for network traffic. It receives network traffic and carries out a deep inspection of each packet. The design and implementation of this novel parser with 5G and multi-tenancy support is a significant enhancement compared to the current state of the art. The output of this sub-component is an extended flow key containing information about inner headers and the packet structure (types of tunneling and encapsulation protocols and tunnel IDs).

Figure 50. Network Self-Protection architecture.

- **Slice definition table:** This table contains the definition of the network slices in OpenFlow format. The left part of the rule is the flow definition matching the slice. The right part of the rule includes the ID of the slice assigned to each flow and the actions performed on the packets before sending them to the Network Slicing Core.
- **Match Flow Action:** This sub-component compares the extended flow key extracted by the 5G multi-tenant traffic classifier against the slice definition table, seeking a network slice matching the packet.
- **Actions and Slice Enforcer:** This sub-component performs the actions associated to each slice before sending the packets to the last module of the pipeline.

- **Network Slicing Core:** This sub-component is in charge of enforcing the network slices in the Data Plane, i.e., on the physical and virtual network interfaces connected to the software data path. Therefore, its primary task is to instantiate network slices and to attach flows to these slices.

6.1.4.3. 5G/6G MULTI-TENANT TRAFFIC CLASSIFIER

In a data plane context, the first step in delivering security mechanisms to secure the infrastructure as well as to offer QoS-guaranteed services is to be able to unambiguously identify the network traffic associated to each user, service, or SLA. This is a significant challenge when dealing with 5G/6G multi-tenant networks. First, using virtualized overlay networks with several levels of nested tunneling and encapsulation protocols (GTP, VXLAN, GRE, GENEVE, ...) entails that the required information about services, tenants or users is being carried in the inner headers. Second, the level of granularity of the traffic associated with a given flow/service/user/tenant differs depending on the use case or stakeholder involved. Existing traffic classifiers in available software data path solutions such as OVS, DPDK, XDP or the Linux Flow Dissector are based on the legacy 5-tuple and therefore do not offer the levels of flexibility and granularity required in 5G/6G multi-tenant networks. Therefore, the first technical contribution of the Network Self-Protection asset to the RIGOUROUS project is a novel traffic classifier addressing this gap in the current state of the art. Figure 51 presents the design of this traffic classifier where all supported network protocols can be seen.

When compared to the existing state of the art, these are the main innovations and differentiating points:

- Support for multi-tenancy capabilities in virtualized infrastructures.
- Capability to parse overlay traffic with encapsulation and tunneling protocols to allow a inspection of the outer and inner headers.
- Efficient design with a modular architecture with re-entrance between modules to optimize the parsing time.

The outcome of this novel traffic classifier embedded as a sub-component in the NSP is an extended flow key (see Figure 51). The legacy Open Flow fields based in the traditional 5-tuple enable the enforcement in the Data Plane of traffic control and security mechanisms based on the information obtained from the outer L2/L3/L4 headers (see Table 1). This is not enough in 5G/6G multi-tenant networks, in which the tenant and end-user information needed to enable a flexible fine-grained data plane programmability is encapsulated and conveyed in the inner headers. For this reason, the traditional 5-tuple-based flow key supported by OVS has been extended with new fields. As listed in Table 2, the new flow key contains 17 new fields (see their length in bytes and a description of the field in the table). The newly extracted metadata includes information about the innermost overlay network in the form of a 6-tuple, the value of the innermost DSCP field as well as information about the overlay networks. The classifier offers support for 8 different tagging and tunneling protocols commonly associated with virtualized networks (see Table 3).

Figure 51. 5G/6G Multi-tenant Classifier architecture.

Table 1. Open Flow fields for traditional 5-tuple based flow key.

Flow Key Field	Length (Bytes)	Field description
<i>ip_src</i>	4	Source Ip address from the outer IPv4 header
<i>ip_dst</i>	4	Destination IP address from the outer IPv4 header
<i>udp_src</i>	2	UPD source port field from the outer UDP header
<i>udp_dst</i>	2	UDP destination port field from the outer UDP header
<i>ip_proto</i>	1	Match the outer IPv4 protocol type (transport protocol)

Table 2. New fields included in the extended 5G/6G flow key.

⁽¹⁾ Mapping between values and protocol listed in Table 3.

⁽²⁾ Meaning of key value for each protocol as given in Table 3.

Flow Key Field	Length (Bytes)	Field description
<i>inner_ip_src</i>	4	Source IP address in the inner IP4 header
<i>inner_ip_dst</i>	4	Destination IP address in the inner IPv4 header
<i>inner_tos</i>	1	Type of Service value (TOS) in inner IPv4 header
<i>inner_port_src</i>	2	Source port in the inner UDP header
<i>inner_port_dst</i>	2	Destination port in the inner UDP header
<i>inner_l3_protocol</i>	2	Ethernet type of the inner layer 3 header
<i>inner_l4_protocol</i>	1	IANA protocol number of the inner layer 4 header
<i>tunnel_type_1</i>	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 1 ⁽¹⁾
<i>tunnel_type_2</i>	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 2 ⁽¹⁾
<i>tunnel_type_3</i>	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 3 ⁽¹⁾
<i>tunnel_type_4</i>	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 4 ⁽¹⁾
<i>tunnel_type_5</i>	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 5 ⁽¹⁾
<i>tunnel_key_1</i>	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 1 ⁽²⁾
<i>tunnel_key_2</i>	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 2 ⁽²⁾
<i>tunnel_key_3</i>	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 3 ⁽²⁾
<i>tunnel_key_4</i>	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 4 ⁽²⁾
<i>tunnel_key_5</i>	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 5 ⁽²⁾

Table 3. Parsing of encapsulation, tunneling and tagging protocols. Tunnel type values and meaning of the key values.

Encapsulation Protocol	Value	Tunnel key description
VXLAN	1	VXLAN Network ID (VNI)
GTP	2	Tunnel Endpoint Identifier (TEID)
GRE	3	GRE Key
MPLS	4	MPLS Label
VLAN	5	VLAN Identifier (VNI)
NSH	6	Service Path Identifier (SPI)
VXLAN-GPE	7	VXLAN Network ID (VNI)
GENEVE	8	Virtual Network Identifier (VNI)

Figure 52 provides an excerpt of the log information generated by the NSP traffic classifier in the Linux Kernel Ring Buffer. It can be noticed how a Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) has been carried out on a packet carrying multi-tenant traffic comprised by 10 headers and the payload. The extended 7-tuple corresponding to the inner headers (end-user metadata) as well as information about the tunneling/encapsulation stack (GTP over VXLAN in this example) has been collected.

Figure 52. Network Self-Protection 5G/6G multi-tenant classifier log.

6.1.4.4. EMPIRICAL EVALUATION AND VALIDATION (PRELIMINARY RESULTS)

This subsection presents the preliminary empirical tests and results collected to evaluate the performance of the Network Self-Protection RIGOUROUS asset. On one hand, the novel 5G/6G multi-tenant classifier integrated in the NSP architecture is essential to provide enhanced fine-grained traffic classification, thereby enabling security rules based on network slicing in 5G/6G networks as a mitigation mechanism. On the other hand, an extra overhead is introduced as delay when processing network traffic. This extra delay is a direct effect of performing a DPI of the traffic and producing a larger flow key, which implies a higher amount of memory and longer time needed to compare the extracted flow key against the security rules in the Slice Definition table.

Figure 53 illustrates the average delay introduced by the proposed software datapath agent compared with the original OVS implementation when ranging the packet size from 256 to 1500 bytes at 1 Gbps for different traffic profiles (IP, LTE/4G, multi-tenant and 5G/6G multi-tenant). For traditional IP traffic with no encapsulation, the behavior is almost similar for both implementations, which indicates a significant efficiency of the new features introduced. Regarding more complex traffic profiles, the associated extra delay for the most challenging traffic (5G/6G multi-tenant traffic with 10 headers and 2 encapsulations) is less than 0.3 microseconds (the difference between around 1.9 microseconds for such demanding traffic and around 1.6 microseconds for pure IP traffic), which is insignificant.

Figure 53. Extra overhead introduced by the 5G multi-tenant multi-domain classifier compared with the traditional 5-tuple traffic classification performed by OVS.

Given that 5G/6G networks are constantly changing scenarios and evolving environments, a challenging feature for the NSP is flexibility and rapid adaptability to such highly demanding scenarios. Figure 54 provides an analysis of the scalability of the NSP when creating a large number of slicing-based security rules, varying the slices enforced on the data plane from 256 to 2048. It provides a breakdown of the time taken for resources provisioning (blue color in the stacked bars) and the time needed to attach a flow to a given network slice (orange color in the stacked bars). Regarding slice creation, the Network Slicing Core is responsible for this task involving the provisioning of the necessary network resources (bandwidth and priority), memory (packet queues) and computational resources (queue disciplines) to meet the SLAs defined in the slice definition. In relation to the attachment of network flows to network slices, the slice definition engine is in charge of receiving OpenFlow messages from the slice manager with the security rule (flow definition and ID of the slice to be attached to). This information is added as a new entry in the Slice Definition table.

Figure 54. Empirical analysis of the NSP scalability: time to enforce security rules based on slicing (resource provisioning and flow attachment to existing slices).

As can be observed in Figure 54 the average time to create a network slice is around 0.12 seconds for 256 slices and roughly 0.9 seconds for the worst-case scenario with 2048 slices. It can also be inferred from Figure 54 that the most time-consuming task to enforce a slice in the data plane is to allocate the needed resources. That makes perfect sense given that this task implies several system calls to the Linux kernel to check the available resources and to provision data structures, queues, and memory. On the other hand, attaching a flow to a network slice is a simpler and less time-consuming time since it involves only inserting a new entry in the Slice Definition table.

To close this subsection, based on the empirical results presented, the NSP demonstrates to be a promising RIGOUROUS asset able to deliver enhanced and resilient data plane programmability for 5G/6G multi-tenant networks, enabling the deployment of slicing-based security policies, while introducing very low extra overhead (a few microseconds) and achieving good scalability when dealing with a large number of network slices (up to 2048).

7 NEXT STEPS

In this deliverable the first prototype and preliminary results from the components were described, which are involved in assuring the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment. The next phase of the task is to be continued in D3.3 with integrations to the RIGOUROUS framework and further development. Deliverable D3.3 will be hence aligned to this deliverable and will have the tentative improvements as listed in Table 4 below:

Table 4. Summary of WP3 current status and next steps.

Task	Asset	Current status	Next step	Partners involved
Human-centric security and privacy modeling and onboarding	Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps	Privacy risk management policy onboarding and delivery for enforcement	Enforcement implementation and feedback for the continuous loop	ITAV
	Onboarding tools	First prototype with OpenSlice, ETSI OSM, and OpenStack + Kubernetes	Development of northbound API or direct contribution to OpenSlice as open-source	ITAV
	Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management	Initial implementation	Iterative improvement, based on any gaps that are identified	ITAV
AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum	Security Orchestration	First prototype & integration of several kind of security policies	Prototyping refinement & preliminary results & full integration in RIGOUROUS and use cases Devising new algorithms for orchestration	UMU
	FL for Anomaly Detection	First prototype validated in testbed	Integration with RIGOUROUS framework and evaluation in use cases	UMU

	Orchestration			
	Bootstrapping and onboarding	Specification Done	Refinements of the Specification (if applicable)	LNVO
		Support specification	Bootstrapping integration with privacy credentials ABC system	UMU
Zero trust and Smart security management	Trust Evaluation and Enabler	Specification Done along with unit tests to identify one attack	Extension of unit tests to cover additional attack scenario(s)	LNVO
End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing	Slice Manager	First prototype & preliminary results & integration	Prototyping refinement & full integration in RIGOUROUS framework and use cases	UWS
	Network Self Protection Component	First prototype & preliminary results & integration	Prototyping refinement & full integration in RIGOUROUS framework and use cases	UWS

8 CONCLUSION

Finally, in conclusion, an extensive summary of the preliminary findings and design prototypes for multiple solutions targeted at improving security and trust in multi-domain 6G networks are provided in this deliverable along with the initial implementation results. The principal contributions are:

- Human-Centric Security, Privacy Modeling, and Onboarding: Comprehensive security and privacy models, user-friendly DevSecOps tools, and robust onboarding processes are being developed to ensure secure and private network applications. In addition to that, Federated Learning frameworks and improved policy translation tools are added features are developed to strengthen the security architecture of the RIGOUROUS framework.
- AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum: AI-driven security orchestration is being implemented for dynamic and adaptive security management spanning IoT, RAN, edge, core, and cloud. Security of devices and applications in a variety of network contexts is improved with the implementation of trusted application onboarding procedures and IoT bootstrapping techniques.
- Zero Trust and Smart Security Management: Development of a standalone Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service Framework (TESF) to assign trust scores based on violation data and statistics collected from the network entities. This aids in proactive risk management and dynamic response to security threats, leveraging AI-driven decision engines for enhanced threat mitigation.
- End-to-End Multidomain Multi-Tenant 6G Slicing: Deployment of security agents and slice controllers to ensure secure network slices across different domains. These components play crucial roles in monitoring, managing, and enforcing security policies, thereby maintaining the integrity and security of multi-domain network slices.

Overall, these initial results and design prototypes lay a foundation for developing an overall secure, trust-oriented, and efficient 6G network environment through RIGOUROUS.

7 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Table 5 List of abbreviations and acronyms.

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
HTTP/HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol/Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
UML	Unified Modeling Language
MSPL	Medium-level Security Policy Language
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
SDN	Software Defined Networks
OpenC2	Open Command and Control
FL	Federated Learning
IP	Internet Protocol Address
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
SQA	Software Quality Assurance
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
UI	User Interface
OSS	Operations Support System
NSaaS	Network Slices as a Service
NFVO	Network Functions Virtualization Orchestrator
VNF	Virtual Network Function
TMF	Tele Management Forum
NS	Network Service
MANO	Management and Orchestration
SCUI	Service Composition UI
PUI	Human Controllable Privacy
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization

NSDs	Network Service Descriptor
AOUI	Application Onboarding UI
PCF	Policy Control Function
SSLAs	Security Service Level Agreement
SPs	Security Policies
HSPL-OP	High-level Technology-Agnostic Policy Models
SO	Security Orchestrator
MTD	Moving Target Defense
SMUI	Security Formal Modeling
ReMUI	Response-Mitigation Policies
RM	Response-Mitigation
DSC	Dynamic Service Composer
VC	Verifiable Credentials
PDL	Permissioned Distributed Ledger
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
NPN	Non-Public Networks
UE	User Equipment
DID	Decentralized IDentifier
L-RMS	Ledger Role-Based Registration Management Service
DPRS	DID Operational participants registry service
DTMF	Dual Tone Multi-Frequency
DRS	DID Resolver service
DDRS	DID Document Registry service
VDRS	VC Data Registry service
DVMS	DID verification management service
NAI	Network Access Identifier
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function

TSP	Trusted Service Provider
IDP	Identification Service Provider
MAC	Medium Access Control
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDR	Unified Data Repository
SUPI	Subscription Permanent Identifier
IMSI	International Mobile Subscription Identity
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
OAI	Onboard Assistance Information
IoT	Internet of Things
RAN	Radio Access Network
E2E	End-to-End
HSPL-OP	High-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policy
ISM	Intent-based Security Management
MSPL-OP	Medium-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policies
D2D	Device-to-Device
ABC	Attribute Based Credentials
UEPK	UE Public Key
DCS	Default Credential Server
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
SBI	Service Based Interface
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
MSK	Master Session Key
SMC	Security Mode Command
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
SEAF	SEcurity Anchor Function
NEF	Network Exposure Function
5G-GUTI	5G- Globally Unique Temporary UE Identity

URSP	UE Route Selection Policy
CAS	Certified Application Server
TESF	Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler service
PDU	Packet Data Unit
5G SA	5G Standalone
gNB	gNodeB
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SPD	Security Policy Database
SAD	Security Association Database
SA	Security associations
NSP	Network Services Platform
DP	Data Plane
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
OF	Open Flow
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
QoS	Quality of Service
XDP	eXpress Data Path
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
NBI	North-Bound Interface
SLA	Service Level Agreement

10 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 System Capabilities.	8
Figure 2 System Enablers.	8
Figure 3 System Software and API.	9
Figure 4 UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram.	9
Figure 5 Security Policy models definition in System Model schema.	10
Figure 6 SPD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema.	11
Figure 7 SAD definition for Security Policy in System Model schema.	11
Figure 8 CommandControlRuleAction definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.	12
Figure 9 CommandControlActionType definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.	12
Figure 10 CameraRuleParameters definition for Command and Control in System Model schema.	12
Figure 11 FilterFLConfigurationCondition definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.	13
Figure 12 AggregatorParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.	13
Figure 13 LearningParameters definition for Federated Learning in System Model schema.	14
Figure 14 Lifecycle of the policy in the orchestrator.	15
Figure 15 FirewallRuleAction definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema.	15
Figure 16 FirewallActionType definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema.	15
Figure 17 RuleParameters definition for VyOS firewall in System Model schema.	16
Figure 18 The onboarding diagram.	18
Figure 19 Application onboarding follows a typical OpenSlice flow.	20
Figure 20 Security Onboarding via Intent-based Security Formal Modeling.	20
Figure 21 Security Onboarding via Security Orchestrator.	20
Figure 22 Risk Model onboarding via the Risk Management UI.	21
Figure 23 Response Playbooks onboarding via the Response-Mitigation Policies into the Response-Mitigation.	21
Figure 24 Service Composition via the SCUI into the Dynamic Service Composer.	21
Figure 25 Dependencies on the onboarding sequence.	22
Figure 26 Decentralized Identification and Trust management framework (DTMF).	23
Figure 27 DID verification for DID holder authentication and authorization.	26
Figure 28 DID/SSI based Subscription Onboarding for Network Access during Registration Procedure.	29
Figure 29 Security Orchestrator.	35
Figure 30 NANCY Profile.	36
Figure 31 UE Initial Registration to Onboarding Network.	37
Figure 32 NANCY credential generation and provisioning.	38
Figure 33 UE DID document (NANCY ID) registration.	39
Figure 34 UE registration in a Serving Network with NANCY ID.	40
Figure 35 Trusted application onboarding with NANCY ID.	42
Figure 36 Prototype design of Trust Evaluation and Trust Enabler Service function.	45

Figure 37 Joint Histogram of the distribution of AMF CPU percentage under the influence of attack (red) and in normal state (blue). Measured for 5.5 mins in linuxenv.	46
Figure 38 Attack Scenario and workflow of the ZTM.	47
Figure 39 Prometheus Rules.	47
Figure 40 Action of the Alert Manager.	48
Figure 41 TESP Server response to attacks.	49
Figure 42 STIX data format for reporting trust scores.	49
Figure 43 Orchestration of channel-protected security slices.	50
Figure 44 SPD configuration message from controller to device.	53
Figure 45 SAD configuration message from controller to device.	54
Figure 46 Time results for the installation of IPsec tunnels using different working modes of the SDN controller.	55
Figure 47 Slice Manager architecture and JSON messages for network slice creation.	57
Figure 48 Slice Manager architecture and JSON messages for flow attachment.	58
Figure 49 Different types of traffic in multi-tenant overlay networks as a consequence of the encapsulation/decapsulation process: IP, LTE traffic and 5G/6G multi-tenant traffic.	60
Figure 50 Network Self-Protection architecture.	62
Figure 51 5G/6G Multi-tenant Classifier architecture.	64
Figure 52 Network Self-Protection 5G/6G multi-tenant classifier log.	66
Figure 53 Extra overhead introduced by the 5G multi-tenant multi-domain classifier compared with the traditional 5-tuple traffic classification performed by OVS.	67
Figure 54 Empirical analysis of the NSP scalability: time to enforce security rules based on slicing (resource provisioning and flow attachment to existing slices).	68

11 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Open Flow fields for traditional 5-tuple based flow key.	66
Table 2 New fields included in the extended 5G/6G flow key	66
Table 3 Parsing of encapsulation, tunneling and tagging protocols. Tunnel type values and meaning of the key values.	67
Table 4 Summary of WP3 current status and next steps.	71
Table 5 List of abbreviations and acronyms.	74

12 REFERENCES

- [1] Amir Javadpour et al., "Deliverable 2.2 - RIGOUROUS Use-Cases".
- [2] VyOS - Open source router and firewall platform. (s. f.). VyOS. <https://vyos.io/>
- [3] ETSI GS PDL 012 (V1.1.1): "Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL); Reference Architecture".
- [4] ETSI GS PDL 023 (V1.1.1): "PDL service enablers for Decentralized Identification and Trust Management".
- [5] 3GPP TS 23.502: "Procedures for the 5G System (5GS) "
- [6] Open VSwitch (OVS) official web site. Available at [HTTPS://WWW.OPENVSWITCH.ORG/](https://www.openvswitch.org/)
- [7] D. Kreutz, F. M. V. Ramos, P. E. Veríssimo, C. E. Rothenberg, S. Azodolmolky and S. Uhlig, "Software-Defined Networking: A Comprehensive Survey," in Proceedings of the IEEE, vol. 103, no. 1, pp. 14-76, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2014.2371999
- [8] Open Networking Foundation (ONF), "OpenFlow Switch Specification Version 1.5.1 (Protocol version 0x06)". [Online], Available at: <https://opennetworking.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/openflow-switch-v1.5.1.pdf>
- [9] The Linux Foundation Projects, "OpenDayLight official web site". [Online], available at: <https://www.opendaylight.org/>
- [10] Open stack networking, Neutron, [Online]. Available: <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Neutron>
- [11] Open Network Operating System (ONOS), Technical steering team (TST)," [Online]. Available: <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>
- [12] "Openstack official web site". [Online], Available at: <https://openstack.org>